

D1.4 Rural Attractiveness: Post-Needs Gathering Update

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Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any errors or omissions.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the implementation of the second stage of Task 1.1 *Rural Attractiveness: Post Needs-Gathering Update*.

This deliverable seeks to update the rural attractiveness's vision or definition, which was created in the first stage of Task 1.1, through: (i) comparison of regional development levels and degree of urbanisation; (ii) cross-border comparison of the pilot survey results obtained as part of Task 4.3 *Regional Needs Gathering & Analysis*; (iii) comparison of the differences observed in the collected survey responses; (iv) the identification of weaknesses and needs of each pilot on the basis of SWOT results implemented as part of T4.3; and (v) the ranking of regional needs further specified in Task 4.4 *Needs-Policy Mapping*.

The results show that there are significant differences among the pilot regions and it is these differences that ultimately determine rural attractiveness in a given territory. The initial definition¹ proposed in D1.1 *Envisioning More Attractive Rural Places and Professions* is broad enough to capture all the identified inter-regional differences at macro-level. But as the project develops, it may be far more productive to encourage regions to develop their own unique concept or concepts of rural attractiveness. One that is based on their own needs, aligned with their own values, sense of identity and vision of the future. The final edition of this deliverable (D1.7) will reflect on the changes in the definition of rural attractiveness that will emerge in the wake of policy evaluation to be conducted as part of T4.5.

Keywords

Rural attractiveness, survey, SWOT, needs, regions.

¹ Rural attractiveness encompasses sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment. There is an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced.

Introduction

This deliverable provides an update of the initial definition of rural attractiveness presented in the D1.1 *PoliRural Vision for Attractive Rural Places and Professions*. The main input for this update comes from T4.3 *Regional Needs Gathering and Analysis*, as well as some additional information and data obtained from the Task 4.4 *Needs-Policy Mapping*.

Methodological differences between the two versions are as follows:

- D1.1 was based mainly on literature review and pilot input at the workshop plus internal survey
- D1.4 is based on external PoliRural survey results (1296 responses) and SWOTs, which have been compiled as part of Task 4.3 *Regional Needs Gathering and Analysis*; as well as D4.4 *Needs-Policy Canvas*, which summarises the results of the Task 4.4 *Needs-Policy Mapping*
- Analysis of statistical information from Eurostat database to inform D1.4 conclusions

The multi-dimensional nature of rural attractiveness initially outlined in D1.1 was recently investigated through a large-scale survey by asking questions on:

- Public services
- Recreation and social activities
- Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living
- Demographic and human capital
- Business, economy and innovation
- Culture and society
- Environment and biodiversity

Key research questions investigated in this deliverable are:

- What has been the impact of T4.3 results on the initial definition?
- What similarities/differences can be identified from the cross-pilot comparison?

Answers to these questions allowed the consortium to:

- Compare changes in pilot positions toward rural attractiveness
- Assess the need for a new definition
- Estimate the impact of future results, namely the outcome of policy evaluation, on the definition of rural attractiveness

1. Methodology and methods

1.1 Methodology

The development of PoliRural’s vision and definition of rural attractiveness is an ongoing process executed in several stages, each of which is based on the results of other project work packages.

At each stage of creation of the definition of rural attractiveness, there has been a basic goal – to capture rural development processes through rural attractiveness as a concept. This results in an understanding of attractiveness based on a “professional” view (based on scientific literature and ideas held by expert groups) approach and a “public” one based on popular perception of attractiveness. D1.1 focused more on the agricultural contexts of rural development, D1.4 - more on regional differences based on regional characteristics and regional needs, which is more a “public” view of rural attractiveness. It is also determined by the methods used - survey, stakeholders’ mapping, needs prioritization, SWOT analysis. The “Professional” view is based on the statistical analysis of the pilot regions and the literature on the quality of life and wellbeing. This deliverable reports on the second stage of developing the vision, which involved the following (Figure 1).

Figure 1 The steps of second stage for updating of the initial definition of rural attractiveness

This deliverable is based on WP4 Current Rural Situation and in particular T4.2 Stakeholder Mapping & Regional Panel Setup, T4.3 Regional Needs Gathering & Analysis, T4.4 Needs-Policy Mapping. The stakeholder mapping methodology was

developed in T4.2, and contained an internal deliverable which outlined a series of steps to guide pilots in the selection process:

1 Stakeholder mapping:

- Identification phase;
- Analysis phase;
- Mapping phase;
- Prioritization phase;

2 Regional Panel Setup;

3 Guidelines for reporting stakeholder engagement.

The methodology creates the foundation for the participatory regional development process, targeting vulnerable groups, representatives of public sector, private sector, research sector, third sector (NGOs, non-profit organizations, civil society organizations, international NGOs, formal and informal associations). The aim is also to cover different fields of operation e.g. rural industries with farming, crafts, service, representation of social needs (NGOs, public agencies), nature conservation, structural conditions (transport, broadband, food processing) etc.

Specific choices are determined by different regional needs, regional scale and other factors. This has led to the identification of relevant stakeholders from the following areas: tourism, primary sector (agriculture, forestry, fishery), manufacturing & industry, ICT, environment & bioresources, youth issues & education, business and farming support, local & regional development, other services.

T4.3 resulted in D4.2 Grassroot Needs & Factors of Rural Attractiveness, while T4.4 - D4.4 in Needs-Policy Canvas. Methodology and guidelines for T4.3 and T4.4 are developed in the D1.3 Needs Gathering & Policy Mapping Template. It provided guidelines for pilot interviews, surveys, SWOT analysis and Policy Mapping. D1.4 is based on D4.2 and D4.4 and the underlying methodology for needs analysis described in D1.3.

The statistical data used for comparison of PoliRural regions, except Galilee (Israel), was obtained from the Eurostat database².

According to Eurostat (2019), the degree of urbanisation can be classified based on the following three categories:

- cities, otherwise referred to as densely populated areas
- towns and suburbs, otherwise referred to as intermediate density areas
- rural areas, otherwise referred to as thinly populated areas

‘Urban areas’ refers to an aggregate composed of information covering cities as well as towns and suburbs.

Eurostat (2019) considered that there are close links between the border typology and the urban-rural typology as each border region is classified as a predominantly urban,

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions/data/database>

intermediate or predominantly rural region. Some border regions may also be classified as mountain regions.

The pilot regions of PoliRural are presented by regions with various types or degrees of urbanisation (Table 1).

No	Pilot region/ Country	Degree of urbanisation of the region
1	Flanders/ Belgium	Intermediate region
2	Monaghan/ Ireland	Predominantly rural region
3	Cuenca/ Spain	Predominantly rural region
4	Vidzeme/ Latvia	Predominantly rural region
5	Mazowieckie/ Poland	Intermediate region
6	Central Bohemia/ Czechia	Predominantly urban region
7	Slovakia	Intermediate region
8	Hame/ Finland	Intermediate region
9	Central Greece/ Greece	Predominantly rural region
10	Apulia/ Italy	Predominantly urban region
11	North Macedonia	Intermediate region
12	Galilee/ Israel	Predominantly rural region

Table 1 The degree of urbanisation of the PoliRural pilot region

Territorial classifications³ obtained for pilots are presented in Table 2.

Pilot region name	Data from the Eurostat database	
	Pilot region name and NUTs level	NUTS upper level
Flanders/ Belgium	BE2 Vlaams Gewest NUTS 1	
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	CZ02 Střední Čechy NUTS 2	CZ0 Česká Republika NUTS 1
Monaghan/ Ireland	Monaghan LAU	IE041 Border NUTS 3
Central Greece/ Greece	EL64 Sterea Ellada NUTS 2	EL6 Kentriki Ellada NUTS 1
Cuenca/ Spain	ES423 Cuenca NUTS 3	ES42 Castilla-la Mancha NUTS 2
Apulia/ Italy	ITF4 Puglia NUTS 2	ITF SUD NUTS1
Vidzeme/ Latvia	LV008 Vidzeme NUTS 3	LV Latvia NUTS 1
Mazowieckie/ Poland	PL92 Mazowiecki regionalny NUTS2	PL9 Makroregion Województwo Mazowieckie NUTS1
Slovakia	SK Slovakia Slovensko NUTS 1	
Hame/ Finland	FI1C2 Kanta-Häme NUTS 3 FI1C3 Päijät-Häme NUTS 3	FI1C Etelä-Suomi
North Macedonia	MK Severna Makedonija NUTS 1	

Table 2 Pilot region name and identification in the Eurostat database⁴

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions/data/database>

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions/data/database>

For comparison of pilot regions, 24 territorial development indicators were chosen and further analysed (Table 3).

Group of indicators	Indicator of Pilot's region
Basic statistics	Land area, km ²
	Population density, persons/km ²
	Population, number
	Share of working age population in total
	Young-age dependency (population aged 0-14 to population 15-64 years)
	Old dependency (aged 65 and over to population 15 to 64 years)
	Age dependency ratio (aged 0-14 and 65 and more to population aged 15-64)
	Crude birth rate
	Crude rate of net migration plus statistical adjustment
	GDP per capita, EUR
	Unemployment rate, %
	At-risk-of-poverty rate, %
	Unemployment rate, %
	Share of agricultural land from total land area, %
	Share of employees in agriculture from total employment
Agriculture	Share of agricultural land from total land area, %
	Share of employees in agriculture from total employment
Share of population (from 25 to 64 years) by education level	Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (levels 0-2), %
	Upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary and tertiary education (levels 3-8), %
	Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4), %
	Tertiary education (levels 5-8), %
Share of economic activity NACE R2 from total GVA in basic prices	Agriculture, forestry and fishing, %
	Industry (except construction), %
	Construction, %
	Wholesale and retail trade; transport; accommodation and food service activities; information and communication, %
	Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities; professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support service activities, %
	Public administration and defence; compulsory social security; education; human health and social work activities; arts, entertainment and recreation, repair of household goods and other services, %

Table 3 List of statistical indicators of PoilRural Pilot regions located in Europa

1.2 Methods

A mixed research method approach combining qualitative and quantitative techniques was used to update the initial definition of rural attractiveness. The critical thinking

approach (Jackson, 2009) that was used in the first stage was also used in research underpinning the D1.4.

One of the first things that authors of D1.4 had to decide was how to interpret the survey results obtained by T4.3. There are many discussions among scholars and practitioners that focus on the correct usage of the Likert scale, where the neutral response option is the biggest source of dispute surrounding the scale (Heller, 1987; Edwards & Smith, 2014; Willits et al., 2016). Originally offered in an effort to avoid false responses, the neutral response option enabled people who were ignorant about or indifferent to a subject to select no opinion or neutral instead of being forced to choose a response that did not reflect their true beliefs. Although designed with the intention of reducing instances of false responses, studies show that the inclusion of a neutral or “no opinion” option significantly increases the number of people stating they have no opinion when they actually do. Three factors likely influence a participant’s decision to falsely report via the neutral option: cognitive effort, ambivalence, and social desirability.

Edwards & Smith (2014) argue that respondents will be more likely to select neutral response option than report their actual opinion. Kulas et al. (2008) added that options such as “neutral” or “not applicable” can be abused by respondents.

Because the T4.3 survey included such options, the AREI team decided to recalculate the findings by excluding “doesn’t apply” to see their impact on other response categories. Two versions are presented in tables in Annex 1. The first table presents all responses, the second one the recalculated results i.e. without the option “doesn’t apply”.

To facilitate the analysis, we aggregated “strongly disagree” with “disagree” options and “strongly agree” with “agree” ones. The combined tables are presented in Annex 2.

In parallel, the hierarchical clustering was performed. Also known as the hierarchical cluster analysis, the hierarchical clustering is an algorithm that groups similar objects into groups. The method is especially popular in big data research and data mining where the aim is to establish a hierarchy of clusters (Zhang et al., 2017). The basic idea is to group similar elements and separate dissimilar ones. These two requirements are often contradictory and algorithms vary in how they resolve this contradiction (Ackerman & Ben-David, 2016). Generally, the algorithms output dendrograms, which the user can then traverse to obtain the desired clustering. Dendrograms provide a convenient method for exploring multiple clusterings of the data (Ackerman & Ben-David, 2016).

In preparing D1.4, the goal was to create a set of clusters, where each cluster is distinct from one another, and the objects within each cluster are broadly similar. This analysis was performed by comparing (i) the regions’ development state using regional statistics/indicators; and (ii) survey results to clarify how regions influenced responses of the survey.

Complete-linkage clustering is one of several methods of agglomerative hierarchical clustering. At the beginning of the process, each element (in our case, region) is in a

cluster of its own. The clusters are then sequentially combined into larger clusters until all elements end up being in the same cluster. The method is also known as farthest neighbour clustering. The result of the clustering can be visualised as a dendrogram, which shows the sequence of cluster fusion and the distance at which each fusion took place (Everitt et al., 2001).

At each step, the two clusters separated by the shortest distance are combined. The definition of 'shortest distance' is what differentiates the different agglomerative clustering methods. In complete-linkage clustering, the link between two clusters contains all element pairs, and the distance between clusters equals the distance between those two elements (one in each cluster) that are farthest away from each other. The shortest of these links that remains at any step causes the fusion of the two clusters whose elements are involved.

In order to decide which clusters should be combined (for agglomerative), or where a cluster should be split, a measure of dissimilarity between sets of observations is required. In most methods of hierarchical clustering, this is achieved through an appropriate metric (a measure of distance between pairs of observations), and a linkage criterion which specifies the dissimilarity of sets as a function of the pairwise distances of observations in the sets (Legendre & Legendre, 1998).

The choice of an appropriate metric will influence the shape of the clusters, as some elements may be close to one another according to one distance and farther away according to another. Here, the Euclidean distance or Euclidean metric is used. It is the "ordinary" straight-line distance between two points in Euclidean space. It is calculated in Cartesian coordinates (Sorensen, 1948; Legendre & Legendre, 1998).

Dissimilarity is a numerical measure of how different two data objects are.

In hierarchical cluster analysis, dissimilarity is measured by Euclidean distance.

In Cartesian coordinates, if:

$$p = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n) \quad (1)$$

and

$$q = (q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n) \quad (2)$$

are two points in Euclidean n -space, then the Euclidean distance (d) from p to q , or from q to p is given by the Pythagorean formula:

$$d(p, q) = d(q, p) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_i - p_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

In our study, $n=24$ (number of regional variables). p and q are pairwise regions.

In data mining, **Z-score** is a method of standardisation (or normalisation) for data panels with large differences between the variable averages. For each variable $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$

Z-score $z = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n)$ is calculated as

$$z_i = \frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (4)$$

where μ is the average of x and σ is the standard deviation of x .

In the first stage of PoliRural survey's responses clustering we use combined data (Annex 2) valued as -1, 0, 1, where response category - 'don't apply' was excluded.

Taking into account that respondents from the predominantly urban and intermediate regions have selected the 'neutral' option, in some cases reaching more than 50% of the total, the hierarchical cluster analysis was performed, excluding neutral position.

The same approach—difference of survey's responses, as natural value between positive (strong agree + agree) and negative (strong disagree + disagree)—was calculated and used for the final comparison among pilot regions (Figures 14-27)

2. Characteristics and comparison of PoliRural pilot regions

The name and country of the PoliRural pilot region, and spatial location is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The name, number and spatial location of Polirural pilot regions

The following PoliRural pilots (see chapter 1) are indicated as predominantly rural regions: Monaghan/ Ireland, Cuenca/ Spain, Vidzeme/ Latvia, Central Greece/ Greece and Galilee/ Israel according Eurostat territories typology.

Reading the brief description of regions (Table 4) and comparing the share of gross value added by economical activity in the particular region (Figure 3), only a few of them can be considered as rural regions—Cuenca, Vidzeme and Galilee. More precise and detailed information of pilot regions see in the D4.4 ‘Needs-Policy Canvas’.

However, the Monaghan region is less populated in Ireland, main economical activities in the region are service and manufacturing, including construction, only 3% is agricultural production.

Although in Central Greece agriculture is developed, other economic activities have a higher impact on region's economy and development (Figure 2). Besides, it is located very closely to the urban centre (Table 4), which also can influence region's development and attractiveness. Cuenca region with the large area of mountainous terrain as well as a low population density is more focused on local services (Figure 2; Table 4).

Pilot region name / Country		Brief description
PoliRural project	Eurostat	
Flanders/ Belgium	Vlaams Gewest	Vlaams Gewest – very densely populated region, with large cities (Antwerp, Ghent, Bruges, Leuven), the seat of the Flemish parliament is located in Brussels, diversified modern economy, good public transport connections. High incomes, low unemployment. Flanders is the Belgian region with the greatest industrial rate, attractive - positive net migration. ⁵
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	Střední Cechy	Střední Čechy – Region's position significantly influences its economic characteristic (immediate proximity to Prague, surrounds Prague), dense transportation network, large industrial enterprises (Skoda), also highest proportion of agricultural land among other Czech regions, attractive - positive net migration. ⁶
Monaghan/ Ireland	Monaghan	Border – located along the Ireland-United Kingdom border, steadily increasing population, although it remains on average the slowest growing region in the country, the second lowest population density in the country, the lowest per capita GDP in the country. Services account for 64.1% of the regional economy, followed by Manufacturing and Construction at 32.8% and Agriculture at 3%. The region is largely rural. ⁷
Central Greece/ Greece	Stereia Ellada	Stereia Ellada - located at the heart of Greece, proximity to the capital city of Athens, dominated by the manufacturing sector, the region is also an important agricultural centre. The region is characterised by geographical and economic heterogeneity, with urban areas being more developed than the rural and mountainous zones. High unemployment rate. ⁸
Cuenca/ Spain	Cuenca	Cuenca – low population density due to the large area of mountainous terrain. Local commerce and services are the main economic activities, also agriculture. Very well connected with Madrid. ⁹
Apulia/ Italy	Puglia	Puglia – long coastline, the per capita GDP is low compared to the national average, the share of the agricultural and services sectors is above the national average, high unemployment rate. The greatest manufacturing specialisations are found in the manufacturing of food products, textiles and metal products. ¹⁰
Vidzeme/ Latvia	Vidzeme	Vidzeme – low population density, negative net migration, generally, the region is characterised by a low building density and a high proportion of natural landscapes with low human impact. The highest added value in region is generated from manufacturing, agriculture, forestry, fishing (the region has the highest primary sector share among all regions), wholesale and retail industries, GDP per capita is lower than the national average.

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/flanders>

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/central-bohemia>

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Border_Region

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/region-stereia-ellada>

⁹ <https://www.britannica.com/place/Cuenca-province-Spain>; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Madrid>

¹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/puglia>

Pilot region name / Country		Brief description
PoliRural project	Eurostat	
Mazowieckie/ Poland	Mazowiecki regionalny	Mazowiecki regionalny – Despite its statistical separation from the Warsaw capital region, the Mazowieckie region will continue to benefit from the proximity to the capital. The share of industry including construction in the generation of regional GVA was estimated for the year 2017 at 41.0%, which was above the national average. Agriculture and other branches of the primary sector accounted for 10.5% of GVA, which was more than three times higher than the national average of 3.1%. A sector with huge potential in the region is the food industry drawing on favourable natural and environmental conditions, large absorptive capacity of the market, leadership in agriculture production and construction sector, and not least the presence of mineral deposits and raw materials. ¹¹
Slovakia	Slovensko	Slovakia has seen significant GDP growth in recent decades, but high territorial inequalities. GDP per capita in Bratislava is now almost 3.5 times higher than in East Slovakia. Youth unemployment is three times higher in eastern Slovakia than in western Slovakia. There is a high degree of centralization - 9.6% of total public investment was carried out by subnational governments compared to an OECD average of 56.9%. ¹² The cost of resources is low. Economic specialization is manufacturing. Lacks the full range of good-quality public services especially in rural areas. Socialization places for young people in rural areas are insufficient. The knowledge infrastructure or the education system for farmers is badly organized, lack of trust. High value of biodiversity conflicting with appropriate management.
Häme/ Finland	Kanta-Häme & Päijät- Häme	Häme – centrally located near largest population and economic centers in Finland, good connection to Helsinki. The landscape in the region is dominated by green forests and unspoiled pure lakes. Economy is dominated by industry - metal industry, food industry, wood processing. ¹³
North Macedonia	Severna Makedonija	Severna Makedonija (NM) – comparatively low GDP per capita, high unemployment rate, high share of agriculture, a comprehensive extension service is lacking. The professional technical support in farming is very poor both in content and also in the process of delivery. The young population is leaving rural areas, seeking better future in towns or abroad. At the same time, NM is a transit point for migrants entering Europe.
Galilee/ Israel	n/d	Galilee – peripheral region, verdant region of rolling hills and rich agricultural valleys. With most of the population of the Region living in small towns and villages, accessibility—both intra-regional and between rural and urban areas—is challenging. Growing population, Israel is a young society compared to the western economies, a primary driver for this age structure is the high fertility rate in Israel. The age structure varies with type of locality as the rural population tends to have more children and a younger age structure.

Table 4 Brief description of PoliRural pilot regions

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/base-profile/mazowieckie-regional>

¹² <https://www.oecd.org/cfe/SLOVAK-REPUBLIC-Regions-and-Cities-2018.pdf>

¹³ <https://www.hamechamber.fi/hame-region-in-brief>

Figure 3 Share of gross value added at basic prices by PoliRural pilot regions, 2017

The content of Table 5 shows differences among regions by considering not only the unemployment rate, but also cross-border gender differences (unemployment rates of males and females).

The rates of economic activity (Figure 4), at-risk-of-poverty rate (Figure 5), as well as usage of the computers (Figure 6) all show regional differences of up to 40%. Besides, the fact that Europe is falling behind other world regions in terms of high-speed internet, which affects its ability to innovate, including in rural areas, as well as on the on-line dissemination of knowledge and on-line distribution of goods and services (EC, 2010).

Region/ Country	Unemployment rates, %		
	Total	Males	Females
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	1.3%	1.2%	1.5%
Flanders/ Belgium	3.2%	3.3%	3.1%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	4.6%	4.2%	5.0%
Monaghan/ Ireland	4.8%	5.0%	4.5%
Slovakia	5.8%	5.6%	6.0%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	6.3%	7.2%	5.4%
Hame/ Finland	6.3%	6.4%	6.2%
Apulia/ Italy	14.9%	13.4%	17.6%
Cuenca/ Spain	16.2%	12.2%	21.3%
Central Greece/ Greece	17.2%	11.8%	25.5%
North Macedonia	17.3%	16.5%	18.4%

Table 5 Unemployment rates (total and by sex) in the PoliRural pilot regions (NUTS 2 regions), 2019

Figure 4 Economic activity rates (from 15 to 64 years) NUTS 2 regions, 2019

Figure 5 At-risk-of-poverty rate by NUTS 2 regions, 2018

Figure 6 Individuals who have never used a computer, 2017

Figure 7 shows clusters or differences of the pilot regions’ sizes. Figure 8 presents clusters or differences among pilot regions territories’, which is an important aspect of the degree of urbanisation.

Figure 7 Scatter diagram of PoliRural pilot regions' population number and land area¹⁴

Figure 8 Scatter diagram of PoliRural pilot regions' density of population and land area¹⁵

The hierarchical clustering results are more precise than scatter diagrams as they identify location similarities and the level of territorial development of the pilot regions.

The clades—in our case the pilot regions—are arranged according to how similar (or dissimilar) they are. Clades are represented through diagrams linking the different regions with connecting lines. Clades that are close to the same height are similar to each other;

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions/data/database>

¹⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions/data/database>

clades with different heights are dissimilar — the greater the difference in height, the more dissimilarity (you can measure similarity in many different ways).

Hierarchical clustering is where a cluster tree (a dendrogram) is built to represent data, where each group (or “node”) links to two or more successor groups. The groups are nested and organized as a tree, which ideally ends up as a meaningful classification scheme. There are two ways to interpret a dendrogram: in terms of large-scale groups or in terms of similarities among individual chunks (Glen, 2015). The rows that are close together (have small dissimilarity) will be linked near the upper side of the plot. For example, we notice the Apulia and Cuenca are very similar (Figure 9). The number of clusters that will be formed by drawing a horizontal line and indicated similarity of clusters (Drout & Smith, 2014).

Comparative results of regional positions on the vertical (y) axis allow one to distinguish clusters that are largely related to the geographical or spatial location. The first cluster includes the Mediterranean countries, the second one – Central European countries, the third cluster Northern countries (Figure 9).

The results of the hierarchical cluster analysis of regional statistics or indicators presented in dendrogram (Figure 10) show that regions Apulia, Cuenca, North Macedonia, Mazowieckie, Hami and Vidzeme more or less fall in the first territorial development cluster. Whereas, Central Greece, Slovakia and Monaghan - in the second cluster, but Central Bohemia and Flanders - in the third cluster (Figure 10).

The exception is the two regions—Flanders and Central Bohemia—with a higher level of development (Figure 10). Regions form one cluster in both cases, comparing the level of development and the position on the vertical axis.

Figure 9 Dendrogram of regions' similarities clusters on the vertical axis (z scores of regional indicators)

Figure 10 Dendrogram of territorial development clusters on the horizontal axis (z scores of regional indicators)

3. PoliRural survey results

3.1 Main results of survey

This deliverable provides an update of the initial definition of rural attractiveness presented in the D1.1 *PoliRural Vision for Attractive Rural Places and Professions* (PoliRural, 2019). The main input for this update comes from PoliRural Task 4.3 *Regional Needs Gathering and Analysis*.

3.2 Comparison survey (responses) results among pilot regions

For comparison of survey responses the correlation-regression analysis was performed with combined data from Annex 2. Results are presented in the Figure 11.

	Slovakia	Central Greece/ Greece	Hame/ Finland	Vidzeme/ Latvia	Monaghan/ Ireland	Central Bohemia/ Czechia	Cuenca/ Spain	Flanders/ Belgium	Galilee/ Israel	Apulia/ Italy	North Macedonia	Mazowieckie/ Poland
Slovakia	0.40	0.32	0.25	-0.43	0.54	0.15	0.22	0.51	0.20	0.19	0.22	0.31
Central Greece/ Greece		0.20	0.24	-0.24	0.42	0.42	0.26	0.32	0.10	0.57	0.26	0.34
Hame/ Finland			0.50	-0.49	-0.02	0.19	0.42	0.54	0.36	0.20	0.42	0.58
Vidzeme/ Latvia				-0.30	0.00	0.42	0.16	0.36	0.11	0.29	0.16	0.81
Monaghan/ Ireland					-0.12	-0.19	-0.47	-0.60	-0.53	-0.17	-0.47	-0.29
Central Bohemia/ Czechia						0.08	0.12	0.24	0.09	0.22	0.12	0.05
Cuenca/ Spain							0.04	0.47	0.04	0.59	0.04	0.46
Flanders/ Belgium								0.28	0.40	0.06	1.00	0.34
Galilee/ Israel									0.52	0.38	0.28	0.46
Apulia/ Italy										-0.02	0.40	0.17
North Macedonia											0.06	0.41
Mazowieckie/ Poland												0.34

Figure 11 Correlation-regression matrix of all responses by pilot regions

Results of the hierarchical cluster analysis of all responses by pilot regions are presented in the dendrogram on the next page (Figure 12). Clustering of similarities shows that the Monaghan region is an independent cluster, because many responses from this pilot are completely opposite to other regions.

Responses from the North Macedonia and the Cuenca are included in the second cluster; the results of Mazowieckie, Central Bohemia and Flanders in the third one; of Galilee and Hame in the fourth cluster; of Apulia and Central Greece in the fifth cluster (Figure 13). Responses of Vidzeme and Slovakia are in the last, sixth cluster.

The dendrogram presented in Figure 12 shows commonalities and differences of the survey responses.

In our opinion these responses are based on the region's development state. Survey responses of less developed—North Macedonia, Cuenca, Galilee, Apulia, Central Greece, Latvia and Slovakia—belong to the first cluster; the second cluster includes responses

from Mazowieckie, Hame and Apulia. The larger and most developed regions' responses are in third cluster, which is located on the right side of horizontal axis.

Figure 12 Dendrogram of responses' similarities clusters (vertical axis)

Figure 13 Dendrogram of responses' commonalities and differences clusters (horizontal axis)

The results of the comparison of survey results show that the strengths and problematic issues can be divided into three groups.

One group includes those responses to the survey questions that differ by the region's degree of urbanisation, size, development state, etc., and which are largely influenced by the rurality of the region.

The second group constitutes those questions (issues) that are common to all regions, regardless of their degree of urbanisation.

The third group of the regional disparities includes questions, where the answers are related to the spatial or territorial location of the region or other circumstances. Presented below are examples of each of the question groups.

The first group is presented by following responses by the pilot region e.g. lack of day-care services (Figure 14), insufficient working people to support the dependent population (Figure 15), insufficient teleworking opportunities (Figure 16) feeling of loneliness and isolation (Figure 17), lack of employment possibilities (Figure 18), lack of spaces to meet for young people (Figure 19) as well recreational activities (Figure 20), and insufficient opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning (Figure 21).

Figure 14 Share of responses to 'There are good day-care facilities in the area' by the pilot

Figure 15 Share of responses to 'There are enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly)' by the pilot

Figure 16 Share of responses to 'There is enough support for teleworking opportunities in the area' by the pilot

Figure 17 Share of responses to 'Loneliness and isolation do not affect many people in the area' by the pilot

Figure 18 Share of responses to 'There are enough possibilities for employment' by the pilot

Figure 19 Share of responses to 'There are enough and well provided spaces to allow young people to meet' by the pilot

Figure 20 Share of responses to 'There are enough recreational activities for young people in the area' by the pilot

Figure 21 Share of responses to 'There are opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area' by the pilot

As mentioned above, the second group of survey questions is more or less important across all pilot regions. For example, the importance of public transport (Figure 22), feelings that sustainable agriculture and forestry is possible to develop in the area (Figure 23), as well as importance of landscapes and environment (Figure 24) are indicated as being of very high importance by respondents in all pilot regions, except Ireland.

Figure 22 Share of responses to 'Public transportation is important to me' by the pilot

Figure 23 Share of responses to 'The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry' by the pilot

Figure 24 Share of responses to ‘Environment and landscapes are important to me’ by the pilot

The third group reflects differences such as territorial location, development state, opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning (Figure 25), support to the eco-firms and sustainable business (Figure 26), lack of adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses (Figure 27).

Figure 25 Share of responses to ‘There are opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area’ by the pilot

Figure 26 Share of responses to ‘The area favours eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy)’ by the pilot

Figure 27 Share of responses to ‘There is an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses in the area’ by the pilot

4. Attractiveness of rural areas in relation to the results of SWOT analysis and needs gathering carried out in the Task 4.3 and Task 4.4

4.1 The main features of rural attractiveness for each pilot

This section provides a glimpse of rural attractiveness, or ways in which it could be achieved, in each of the 12 regional pilots. As rural attractiveness is multi-dimensional in nature, the concept has been divided into seven constituent parts:

1. Availability of public and other services
2. Recreation and/or social activities
3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living
4. Demographic and human capital
5. Business economy and innovation
6. Social and cultural aspects
7. Environment and biodiversity

A “X” sign next to each statement indicates a leverage point that, if addressed correctly, can make a particular region more attractive. Each “pilot fiche” is concluded with a summary of needs that regional stakeholders believe should be tackled as a matter of priority.

4.1.1. Pilot 1 Flanders/ Belgium

1. Availability of public and other services

Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
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2. Recreation / social activities

Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	X
Certain types of recreation require specific infrastructure which is not possible in rural areas due to environmental constraints (e.g. paved paths)	X
Compared to urban areas less variety in recreation/social activities Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	X

3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

The vulnerability of the new poor and widespread uneasy situations, especially among young people and among foreign residents	X
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4. Demographic & human capital

The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly)	X
People have not enough working potential. The education structure of the working population is not in accordance with the needs of businesses	X

New entrants and migrants may have difficulties to get to know people, difficulties to become a part of the community. A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants	X
Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT

7. Environment & Biodiversity

Rural landscape is highly fragmented	X
Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations environmental issues related to agricultural practices	X

Flanders rural attractiveness' needs

The Flanders pilot prioritises climate-smart and innovative agriculture since its agricultural sector needs to deal with the challenges and opportunities related with climate change e.g. drought. It is important to find a balance between nature and agriculture in highly fragmented rural landscape, to support farmers and encourage young and new entrants to gain a foothold in the sector. Policies are needed that would enhance and ensure the heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g. small landscape elements), enhance social inclusion, reduce poverty and improve economic development through e.g. specialised housing and other services for the elderly and poor. Investment in public transport and help further develop rural tourism.

4.1.2. Pilot 2 Monaghan/ Ireland

1. Availability of public and other services

Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Limited broadband access (some areas)	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Compared to urban areas less variety in recreation/social activities Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	X
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3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Housing opportunities are limited & expensive.	X
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4. Demographic & human capital

Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions	X
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Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area	X
---	---

5. Business, economy & innovation

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

Low connections between urban & rural areas	X
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7. Environment & Biodiversity

Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations environmental issues related to agricultural practices	X
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Monaghan rural attractiveness' needs

The Monaghan pilot wants to provide support schemes that encourage new entrants and young people into farming. Another goal is to improve the financial security of farming through greater diversification, access to finance and alternatives to land purchase. To that end, proactive promotion of the rural area to attract newcomers is needed along with encouragement of more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables and forestry development. If Monaghan pilot is to succeed in its ambitions, the region must also address the Brexit uncertainty and increase employment opportunities in rural areas for both existing populations and recent or potential newcomers.

4.1.3. Pilot 3 Cuenca/ Spain

1. Availability of public and other services

Insufficient opportunities for higher or professional education	X
Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Limited broadband access (some areas)	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X
There are no sufficient good medical services	X
Underdevelopment of electricity infrastructure – risk of electricity blackouts and poor access to water management system among rural inhabitants	X
The bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment is heavy (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care)	X
SMEs are too small (=lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities and spaces to meet for young people	X
Lack of well-organized structures of leisure (e.g. thematic parks)	X
Insufficient and little diversified offer of extracurricula for children	X
Certain types of recreation require specific infrastructure which is not possible in rural areas due to environmental constraints (e.g. paved paths)	X
Commercial services in the area are insufficient and poorly diversified	X
Compared to urban areas less variety in recreation/social activities	X

Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	
--	--

3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Some problems with integration of new entrants	X
Living conditions in villages and rural areas (except in tourist areas) are seen as less attractive than in urban areas (LR)	X

4. Demographic & human capital

Activity of the citizens is insufficient to ensure vibrant community growth	X
Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions	X
Limited opportunities to develop family plans.	X
New entrants and migrants may have difficulties to get to know people, difficulties to become a part of the community. A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants	X
Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

General employment opportunities in the area are very limited	X
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6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

The high percentage of the aging population does not facilitate the introduction of social and cultural changes	X
Insufficient number of young people among professional decision takers	X
Poor appreciation and social awareness of the importance of preserving the heritage elements	X

7. Environment & Biodiversity

The landscape richness and natural diversity of the area are not sufficiently valued Lack of professional staff with deeper knowledge and experience in biodiversity valorisation and protection	X
There are no efficient waste management practices by individuals and the business sector - In rural areas and around villages there are numerous unregulated/unorganized waste disposal sites Very low percentage of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste	X

Cuenca rural attractiveness' needs

For the Cuenca pilot, addressing the exodus of young people and women from the region (depopulation) is of paramount importance. To make the region more attractive, policy makers should promote job creation, with special emphasis on young people and women, at the same time focusing on employment in niches related to the circular economy, among others.

They should guarantee quality access to the internet in the territory and improve the training of the population in the use of the internet and telematic services; facilitate business development and entrepreneurship; improve transportation service both within the territory and from the territory to urban areas, with particular attention to transportation to health services; improve the quality of health care service and

encourage vocational and higher education and training, particularly for youth and women.

Cuenca's attractiveness can be further improved by providing sufficient and high-quality services (nurseries, electricity, drinking water, commercial services, fairgrounds, waste treatment services, etc.), by promoting economic diversification through the involvement of public and private sector actors, by adopting a balanced tourism policy, and by harnessing the region's cultural heritage and natural capital.

Last but not least, the development of agribusiness value chain, from raw materials to the local market, is expected to give a much needed boost' to region's development.

4.1.4. Pilot 4 Vidzeme/ Latvia

1. Availability of public and other services

Lack of adequate day care facilities in the area (61%)	X
Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Low intraregional transportation connectedness	X
Limited broadband access (some areas)	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X
SMEs are too small (=lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	X
Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities and spaces to meet for young people	X

3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Housing opportunities are limited & expensive.	X
The vulnerability of the new poor and widespread uneasy situations, especially among young people and among foreign residents	X
Some problems with integration of new entrants	X
Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are not yet sufficiently considered of quality	X
Living conditions in villages and rural areas (except in tourist areas) are seen as less attractive than in urban areas (LR)	X

4. Demographic & human capital

Activity of the citizens is insufficient to ensure vibrant community growth	X
The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly)	X
Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions	X
People have not enough working potential. The education structure of the working population is not in accordance with the needs of businesses	X
New entrants and migrants may have difficulties to get to know people, difficulties to become a part of the community.	X

A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants	
Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

The bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment is heavy (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care)	X
SMEs are too small (lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours	X
No adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development	X
There is a lack of entrepreneurship know-how and skills	X
The lack of relevant and useful networks of entrepreneurs	X
General employment opportunities in the area are very limited	X

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

There are no good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making	X
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7. Environment & Biodiversity

The landscape richness and natural diversity of the area are not sufficiently valued Lack of professional staff with deeper knowledge and experience in biodiversity valorisation and protection	X
Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations environmental issues related to agricultural practices	X

Vidzeme rural attractiveness' needs

The Vidzeme region needs to increase the level of civic participation and public involvement in the promotion of territorial development and implementation of initiatives, including greater involvement of LAGs and other NGOs. Smart specialisation along with investment in the creation of high value-added products and services is expected to provide the much needed boost to rural attractiveness. Interventions in other areas are also needed e.g in lifelong learning and the development of skills and knowledge (digital competences, social and professional skills); in the diversification of business, especially within the framework of the implementation of existing and new CAP, RDP and EC priorities in rural areas, particularly the circular economy; in the housing supply, quality and energy efficiency. Further gains can be made by investing in the accessible public transport and the provision of road infrastructure.

4.1.5. Pilot 5 Mazowieckie/ Poland

1. Availability of public and other services

Low intraregional transportation connectedness	X
Underdevelopment of electricity infrastructure – risk of electricity blackouts and poor access to water management system among rural inhabitants	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	X
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Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities and spaces to meet for young people	X
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3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Some problems with integration of new entrants	X
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4. Demographic & human capital

Activity of the citizens is insufficient to ensure vibrant community growth	X
The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly)	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

No adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development	X
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6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

Lack of gender equality in taking decisions and professional life Rural women have very low levels of decision-making in the family and leadership of family businesses	X
Social exclusion as an increasing problem (Young People)	X
Insufficient number of young people among professional decision takers	X
There are no good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making	X
Building illegal phenomena, damage to historical and archaeological sites, environmental damage	X

7. Environment & Biodiversity

No specific environmental or biodiversity features	X
Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations environmental issues related to agricultural practices	X

Mazowieckie rural attractiveness' needs

The Mazowieckie region has identified a broad range of needs, including waste and water infrastructure, labour market (unemployment), gender and age equality in rural policy making, propitious investment climate for startups and SMEs, reliable and efficient transportation network, more diverse recreational and social offer for all the age groups. It is widely recognised that rural attractiveness cannot be achieved without the provision of support schemes that encourage new young people into farming, without improvements to farming/processing practices that promote the environmentally-friendly food production, environmentally friendly business activities and public services, and without solutions that target problems with the integration of certain groups (young, senior policy) in remote areas. Policy makers must focus on the establishment of cooperation/new schemes to attract relevant stakeholders in the region, with a special focus on the integration of women, youth and potential newcomers. Existing social and political conflicts should be mediated with the involvement of stakeholders across the different sectors. Special measures can be designed to diminish income inequalities – especially in the context of educational opportunities, access to healthcare and access to public services and public goods.

4.1.6. Pilot 6 Central Bohemia/ Czechia

1. Availability of public and other services

Intra-regional differences in capacities of kindergartens and elementary schools, endangered general education in peripheries, capacity insufficiency in suburbs	X
Low intraregional transportation connectedness	X
Limited broadband access (some areas)	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X

2. Recreation / social activities

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Housing opportunities are limited & expensive	X
Air pollution related to using of local fireplaces (namely in areas with no gasification)	X

4. Demographic & human capital

Low level of local identity of newcomers (especially in suburban areas)	X
Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

There is a lack of entrepreneurship know-how and skills.	X
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6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

7. Environment & Biodiversity

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

Central Bohemia rural attractiveness' needs

The Central Bohemian region identified the following leverage points for future interventions aimed at increasing rural attractiveness: ensuring accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region; investing in high-speed internet; developing a balanced (agro)tourism policy; minimising intra-regional disparities; attracting young professionals to work in high-tech/innovative companies and research organizations located in the region; providing sufficient supply of social and health services for the aging population; establishing new high-tech/innovative companies and connecting them with research organizations; supporting the development of start-ups and spin-offs; adapting to the climate change; using environmentally friendly soil and land in practices; and embracing the circular economy and bioeconomy principles. All this is expected to help Central Bohemia become a resilient region that supports the wellbeing of all its inhabitants.

4.1.7. Pilot 7 Slovakia

1. Availability of public and other services

Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X
There are no sufficient good medical services	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities and spaces to meet for young people	X
Lack of well-organized structures of leisure (e.g. thematic parks)	X

3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Housing opportunities are limited & expensive	X
Some problems with integration of new entrants	X
Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are not yet sufficiently considered of quality	X

4. Demographic & human capital

Activity of the citizens is insufficient to ensure vibrant community growth	X
The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly)	X
Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

No adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development	X
General employment opportunities in the area are very limited	X

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

Insufficient number of young people among professional decision takers	X
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7. Environment & Biodiversity

The landscape richness and natural diversity of the area are not sufficiently valued Lack of professional staff with deeper knowledge and experience in biodiversity valorisation and protection	X
Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations environmental issues related to agricultural practices	X

The Slovak pilot rural attractiveness' needs

The Slovak pilot recognises that rural attractiveness is not possible without adequate housing opportunities, without sustainable settlements, regions and landscapes, without access to drinking water, sewage and clean resources, without sustainable urban development that prevents climate change and protects the terrestrial life. In light of this, it is important to promote job creation with adequate pay and with the aim of supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy), to develop a long term vision for the development and stability of rural areas

and agriculture with the aim of restoring their self-sufficiency, to improve transparency of direct payments for farmers and rural development program projects. The pilot is committed to finding ways to support young, family and small farmers, to improve quality of public services, to support tele-working opportunities, improve the mobility possibilities to the main city and the connections between rural and urban areas, increase good medical (primary attention) services and adequate public support for the provision of e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services, simplify the rules for direct sales of products from farms and restore local market halls and places. Rural attractiveness can be further boosted by increasing the number and synergy of local communities, and by promoting local organizations through regional specialties, crafts and traditions.

4.1.8. Pilot 8 Hame/ Finland

1. Availability of public and other services

Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Low intraregional transportation connectedness	X
Limited broadband access (some areas)	X
The bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment is heavy (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care)	X
SMEs are too small (lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities and spaces to meet for young people	X
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3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Some problems with integration of new entrants	X
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4. Demographic & human capital

The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly)	X
Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions	X
New entrants and migrants may have difficulties to get to know people, difficulties to become a part of the community. A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

The bureaucracy in entrepreneurship and providing employment is heavy (tax, public funding, employees, insurances, health care)	X
SMEs are too small (=lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours	X
There is a lack of entrepreneurship know-how and skills.	X
The lack of relevant and useful networks of entrepreneurs	X
General employment opportunities in the area are very limited	X

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

Social exclusion as an increasing problem (Young People)	X
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7. Environment & Biodiversity

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

Häme rural attractiveness' needs

The Häme pilot identified the following as leverage points for boosting the rural attractiveness: supporting the multi-locality in living and working, supporting the new business opportunities in farms and rural areas, investing in education and RDI to enhance circular economy solutions in the field of bioeconomy (from field to field), making it easier for newcomers to get adopted into the community, attracting young people to live and work in Häme region, improving access to public services.

4.1.9. Pilot 9 Central Greece/ Greece

1. Availability of public and other services

Insufficient opportunities for higher or professional education	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X
There are no sufficient good medical services	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Lack of well-organized structures of leisure (e.g. thematic parks)	X
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3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

The vulnerability of the new poor and widespread uneasy situations, especially among young people and among foreign residents	X
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4. Demographic & human capital

Limited opportunities to develop family plans.	X
New entrants and migrants may have difficulties to get to know people, difficulties to become a part of the community. A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

7. Environment & Biodiversity

Lack of informative actions regarding greening measures of CAP.	X
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Central Greece rural attractiveness' needs

The Central Greece region has identified the following priorities for its rural areas: increasing the population especially young people; providing more training opportunities (e.g. seminars, e-learning courses, Lifelong learning training); introducing more

educational and consulting services for gaining digital and technological skills in agriculture; increasing the funding for research and innovation activities; supporting the business environment where start-ups can thrive; guaranteeing the adequate access to the internet in remote areas and increasing the number of free access hot-spots in public places (in ports, schools, sports/recreation areas, churches, etc.); improving the public transportation and accessibility between remote areas within the region; providing funding to the initiatives and organized actions aimed at promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects, agritourism) and effective exploitation of high natural and historical value areas.

4.1.10. Pilot 10 Apulia/ Italy

1. Availability of public and other services

Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	X
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3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

The vulnerability of the new poor and widespread uneasy situations, especially among young people and among foreign residents	X
Some problems with integration of new entrants	X

4. Demographic & human capital

Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions	X
Limited opportunities to develop family plans.	X
New entrants and migrants may have difficulties to get to know people, difficulties to become a part of the community. A progressive decrease in the number of inhabitants	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

No weaknesses indicated in the SWOT.

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

High youth and female unemployment rate	X
Building illegal phenomena, damage to historical and archaeological sites, environmental damage	X

7. Environment & Biodiversity

Environmental degradation phenomena in rural areas Some parts of the region as becoming pollutant	X
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Apulia rural attractiveness' needs

In Apulia region, rural attractiveness requires a concerted effort on several fronts. In particular, the promotion of knowledge transfer and innovation in the agricultural sector and forestry and rural areas; strengthening of farm profitability and competitiveness in all region's agriculture in all its forms; promotion of innovative technologies for farms and sustainable forest management; investment in sustainable food supply chain, including processing and marketing of agricultural products, animal welfare and risk management in the sector agricultural; preservation, restoration and enhancement of the ecosystems connected to agriculture and agricultural forestry; efficient use of resources and the transition to a low-emission economy; boosting the resilience to climate change in the agri-food and forestry sector; and working towards social inclusion and poverty reduction.

4.1.11. Pilot 11 North Macedonia

1. Availability of public and other services

Insufficient opportunities for higher or professional education	X
Lack of adequate day care facilities in the area (61%)	X
Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X
There are no sufficient good medical services	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	X
Lack of adequate offer of free time and recreation activities and spaces to meet for young people	X
Insufficient and little diversified offer of extracurricula for children	X

3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Some problems with integration of new entrants	X
People are not highly aware of the usage of renewable energy for business purposes and in everyday life (55%)	X
Living conditions in villages and rural areas (except in tourist areas) are seen as less attractive than in urban areas (LR)	X
Weak activity or non-existence of regional or local institutions competent for rural development	X

4. Demographic & human capital

Activity of the citizens is insufficient to ensure vibrant community growth	X
The dependency ratio is not sound in the area; there are not enough working people to support the depend population (i.e. children, elderly)	X
People have not enough working potential. The education structure of the working population is not in accordance with the needs of businesses	X
Limited opportunities to develop family plans.	X
Loneliness and isolation affect many people in the area	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

No adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development	X
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General employment opportunities in the area are very limited	X
Inadequate coordination of program and activities directed towards different economic sectors in rural areas	X

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

Lack of gender equality in taking decisions and professional life Rural women have very low levels of decision-making in the family and leadership of family businesses	X
There are no good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making	X

7. Environment & Biodiversity

The landscape richness and natural diversity of the area are not sufficiently valued Lack of professional staff with deeper knowledge and experience in biodiversity valorisation and protection	X
Low compliance of agricultural practice with environmental limitations environmental issues related to agricultural practices	X
There are no efficient waste management practices by individuals and the business sector - In rural areas and around villages there are numerous unregulated/unorganized waste disposal sites Very low percentage of the populations in rural areas receive regular collection services for solid waste	X

North Macedonia rural attractiveness' needs

In the North Macedonian pilot, rural attractiveness can be achieved by developing a framework for coordinated program creation and activities directed towards identifying and incorporating the specific needs of the economic sectors in rural areas, by providing consultancy services for entrepreneurial support (technology, finance, HR, marketing, sales etc), by establishing separate funds for financial support to innovative/new rural activities, by establishing institutions at local or regional level that are competent enough to address the specific needs of the different areas of rural development, by critical issues of high importance for young people e.g. education, day-care, extracurricular activities, employment and career prospects, social and recreational activities, by developing the road infrastructure, by providing better opportunities for higher/professional education, by offering the elderly people recreational activities and spaces to meet and socialize, and by creating measures to encourage youth participation in decision-making.

4.1.12. Pilot 12 Galilee/ Israel

1. Availability of public and other services

Poor infrastructure connections and public transportation services	X
Limited broadband access (some areas)	X
Weak public services, online services in rural areas (e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services)	X
Lack of telework opportunities in the area	X

2. Recreation / social activities

Lack of well-organized structures of leisure (e.g. thematic parks)	X
Compared to urban areas less variety in recreation/social activities	X

Inadequate provision of public services to support the elderly, (retirement homes) disabled and immigrants (social houses)	
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3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living

Housing opportunities are limited & expensive	X
Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are not yet sufficiently considered of quality	X

4. Demographic & human capital

Many of the young people are migrating looking for better employment conditions	X
People have not enough working potential. The education structure of the working population is not in accordance with the needs of businesses	X

5. Business, economy & innovation

SMEs are too small (=lack of resources) to participate large public procurement bid competitions. The bidding requires a lot of working hours	X
General employment opportunities in the area are very limited	X
Jobs in the high-tech sector is very scare and difficult to get, especially for youngsters	X

6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas

Lack of gender equality in taking decisions and professional life Rural women have very low levels of decision-making in the family and leadership of family businesses	X
Low connections between urban & rural areas	X
Insufficient number of young people among professional decision takers	X

7. Environment & Biodiversity

Environmental degradation phenomena in rural areas Some parts of the region as becoming pollutant	X
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Galilee rural attractiveness' needs

The Galilee region has identified climate smart and innovative agriculture as important enablers of rural development. There is also a strong need to strike the right balance between nature and agriculture, to support farmers and encourage young people to immigrate to Galilee, to strengthen higher education institutions, to develop rural tourism and industry, to precipitate region's digitisation and make it more human centric.

4.1 Attractiveness of rural areas

As mentioned in the previous deliverable (D1.1), there is a growing interest in and importance of assessing attractiveness of territories, especially rural ones, from the point of view of their stakeholders, especially inhabitants or potential inhabitants, including new entrants.

Below are some insights from recent literature on what is considered important by rural residents when assessing the attractiveness of rural areas.

Wellbeing, quality of life or well-living, as well as contentment with satisfying the needs of the various socio-demographic groups in rural areas is gaining in importance. The economic development, ensuring wellbeing and well-living of rural inhabitants, can be encouraged by various tools and measures: new and innovative forms of entrepreneurship (multifunctional agriculture, tourism, social entrepreneurship, public services, etc.); new forms of networking and cooperation (social innovations, sharing, crowdfunding, etc.); knowledge and innovations (i.e., vocational education and training, lifelong learning and distance learning, local knowledge), promoting the involvement of young people, women, as well as new entrants (PoliRural, 2019).

‘Attractiveness’ is a complex and multifaceted set of characteristics; the relative balance of factors varies depending on the groups that are at the centre of attraction strategies (Servillo et al., 2012). A key component of research into regional development is the identification of roles that environmental, physical and social attributes play in reinforcing (or diminishing) regional attractiveness for each stakeholder group. Barboric et al. (Barboric et al., 2018) conclude that attractiveness is concentrated always around two main factors: 1) human factor on one side, and 2) business factor on the other, where the human-business sphere can be perfectly mixed with time factors. Kuhmonen et al. (Kuhmonen et al., 2016) have added an immaterial welfare.

Brauer & Dymitrow (2014) pointed-out that the term ‘Quality of life’ is a complex concept that incorporates many different material and immaterial aspects. It refers to the general wellbeing of people, groups or societies, and has been used widely within e.g., healthcare, policy and development. Besides, it is recognised that quality of life does not only refer to income-related living standards of individuals (the economic aspect), but is a wider concept that also includes the surrounding environment, physical and mental health, education, leisure, recreation, social belonging, and so forth (Brauer & Dymitrow, 2014).

Eurostat (2017) considers that quality of life is a broader concept than economic production and living standards. It includes the full range of factors that influences what we value in living, reaching beyond its material side.

It is highlighted by the Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission (Eurostat, 2017) that the well-being and quality of life are inherently multidimensional concepts with a framework encompassing nine dimensions:

1. Material living conditions;
2. Productive or other main activity;
3. Health;
4. Education;
5. Leisure and social interactions;
6. Economic security and personal safety;
7. Governance and basic rights;
8. Natural and living environment;

9. Overall experience of life.

The wellbeing of regional and rural inhabitants is a crucial policy issue (OECD, 2017). OECD identifies some important factors influencing the quality of life, which range from income and jobs to education and civic participation. Many of the most influential factors for people's wellbeing are local issues such as employment, access to health services, pollution and security. OECD (2017) considers that improving lives entails making the places where people live better.

The results of SWOT analysis undertaken as part of T4.3 combined with the work underpinning this deliverable allowed the research team to identify the main dimensions and assets that contribute to rural attractiveness (Figure 28).

Figure 28 Main dimensions & assets creating the rural attractiveness

The choice and assessment of different types of capital and assets usually depends on the size of a given territory (state, region, municipality), and on target/stakeholder groups. The latter can be further differentiated by sector, (e.g. public, NGOs, governmental), field (e.g. agriculture, tourism, forestry, ITC), socio-demographic groups (inhabitants, new entrants/new comers, visitors, etc.; age, gender, prosperity and health state, etc.), education levels (PoliRural, 2019).

As a result, attractiveness becomes “a place-specific asset that guarantees some kind of socio-economic stability”. Nature's benefits to people include the provision of biodiversity and ecosystems (Diaz et al., 2015). By definition, all nature's benefits have human value, which can range from spiritual inspiration to market value. Most benefits, however, depend on the joint contribution of nature and anthropogenic assets (Diaz et al., 2015), and provide to people good quality of life.

The Europe 2020 Strategy recognizes the importance of improving the delivery of environmental services as part of the wider challenge of moving towards a resource-efficient economy (EC, 2010). In the Europe 2020 Strategy, the EU formulated three additional targets: “intelligent growth, sustainable growth, and inclusive growth.” With respect to quality of life, the goal of inclusive growth in turn led to the setting of some explicit social targets. The Europe 2020 Strategy emphasizes the social dimensions in Europe, and brings the economic, labour market policy, and social aspects into greater balance. Inclusive growth encompasses the areas of “financial poverty and living conditions,” “labour market access,” and “education.”

The concept of housing quality describes the attractiveness of residential locations as a central component of quality of life in rural areas. However, rural areas were found to have deficits in the provision of public services. The research also showed that quality of life in rural areas can be problematic for certain groups, in particular the elderly who live alone and have significant limitations in their ability to perform activities of daily living. Educational and job opportunities were rated as lower in rural communities than in larger cities (Moser et al., 2018).

Improving the quality of life is a strategic priority for the EU, and is therefore also a stated goal of development policy for rural areas. The EAFRD Regulation provides the legal framework for this policy (Moser et al., 2018).

Moser et al. (2018) argue that the objectives of political action “quality of life” and “wellbeing” are multidimensional concepts with subjective components. However, a number of problem areas were identified in rural villages that cannot be addressed through an expansion of civic engagement, including poor job prospects, a lack of mobility, a lack of cultural and leisure activities for young people, and challenges in combining work and family (Moser et al., 2018).

Many rural development programmes are not integrated into an overall rural development perspective that considers the quality of life as an essential precondition for any possible development of these areas (Casini et al., 2019).

At the basis of any approach to an economic policy inspired by the principle of sustainable development lies the problem of formalising the very concept of quality of life. According to the utilitarian approach, the level of individual wellbeing is assessable by means of quantifying the goods and services individuals possess, hence the spread of the per capita Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as an indicator of the economic wellbeing of individuals residing in a given country.

Using the per capita GDP as a measurement of wellbeing definitely presents numerous advantages, such as the relative simplicity of its measurement and its effectiveness in making comparisons between countries. It can constitute, however, only a component of the broader concept of quality of life that is becoming established in contemporary societies (Casini et al., 2019).

Conclusions

In order to clarify the rural attractiveness's vision, the following research steps were performed:

1. The pilot regions were compared according to their development indicators by means of the correlation-regression and hierarchical clustering analysis
2. The survey results, obtained as part of Task 4.3 *Regional Needs Gathering & Analysis*, were compared between the regions using hierarchical clustering
3. The differences in survey results were investigated not only by region but also by comparing survey responses of different question groups
4. The weaknesses and needs of each pilot region were identified using survey's SWOT results (T4.3)
5. The regional needs prioritization (Task 4.4 *Needs-Policy Mapping*)

The results show that there are significant differences among the pilot regions considering survey responses, weaknesses and needs. These differences, in our opinion, depend on the region's level of socio-economic development, degree of urbanisation and territorial location, which is perhaps pronounced in terms of security and immigration issues (e.g. Spain, Greece).

We found that the attractiveness of rural areas with a relatively strong agri-food sector and industries such as tourism is mainly formed by the provision of sustainable, good quality of life for the region's residents, entrepreneurs and employees. The sustainability aspect is essential for new entrants or new comers in decision-making, as it links their own and their families' lives to the countryside or region.

Sustainable rural development is possible only when environmental, economic, social, human and cultural assets are fully harnessed and used in the creation of public goods and services. When this happens, rural areas become vibrant, healthy and pleasant places to live, work and visit.

The initial definition of rural attractiveness¹⁶ captures all these requirements. However, as we move forward to the next stage in PoliRural, it will be necessary to reflect the role of wellbeing in the definition of rural attractiveness, not least because this factor emerged as important in both the WP4 results and our the calculations underpinning this deliverable (section 3.2). We can even argue that sustainable level of quality of life, a level that ensures the wellbeing of individuals living and working in the countryside, is a priority for rural attractiveness.

¹⁶ Rural attractiveness encompasses sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment. There is an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced.

How rural attractiveness will be viewed in the future remains to be seen. What is certain is that our thinking on the topic will continue to evolve throughout the project. Future work on evaluation (T4.5 Evaluation of Regional Policy Measures) will provide an occasion to reflect upon the concept of rural attractiveness and the role such concepts have played in recent policy interventions. The main points and lessons learned from the forthcoming evaluation work will enable a more detailed comparison of how the concept is used in recent or ongoing policies. Based on these future findings, we may have to eschew our search for a universal definition in favor of a more flexible, regionally adapted concept of rural attractiveness. Furthermore, we remain very open to the idea of explicitly embedding the development of regionally adapted concepts of rural attractiveness into the vision building process foreseen as part of Future Outlooks (T5.3). This will help to engage local stakeholders, enrich the concept of the vision, and provide a basis for aligning the intervention logic of the action plan with local values and identity as well as a shared vision of an “attractive” future. The final edition of this deliverable (D1.7) will reflect on the changes in the definition of rural attractiveness that will emerge in the wake of evaluation findings.

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Annex 1: Examples of recalculation of PoliRural survey responses' results

Calculated results of respondents' responses¹⁷

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services					
	There are sufficient public transportation to services (hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises, schools, universities):					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	3.82%	21.66%	22.93%	43.95%	6.37%	1.27%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	23.33%	50.00%	16.67%	6.67%	3.33%
Hame/ Finland	38.89%	40.00%	4.44%	10.00%	4.44%	2.22%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	8.20%	25.06%	20.27%	31.44%	11.62%	3.42%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.00%	11.54%	7.69%	48.72%	32.05%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	4.88%	31.71%	12.20%	21.95%	26.83%	2.44%
Cuenca/ Spain	21.05%	43.86%	17.54%	15.79%	0.00%	1.75%
Flanders/ Belgium	14.71%	35.29%	13.73%	23.53%	12.75%	0.00%
Galilee/ Israel	36.00%	52.00%	4.00%	0.00%	4.00%	4.00%
Apulia/ Italy	23.33%	50.00%	16.67%	16.67%	3.33%	6.67%
North Macedonia	17.65%	27.73%	18.49%	29.41%	4.20%	2.52%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	14.71%	35.29%	13.73%	23.53%	12.75%	0.00%
	12.44%	28.90%	17.40%	28.35%	10.71%	2.20%

Recalculated results of respondents' responses

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services				
	There are sufficient public transportation to services (hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises, schools, universities):				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	3.9%	21.9%	23.2%	44.5%	6.5%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	24.1%	51.7%	17.2%	6.9%
Hame/ Finland	39.8%	40.9%	4.5%	10.2%	4.5%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	8.5%	25.9%	21.0%	32.5%	12.0%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.0%	11.5%	7.7%	48.7%	32.1%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	5.0%	32.5%	12.5%	22.5%	27.5%
Cuenca/ Spain	21.4%	44.6%	17.9%	16.1%	0.0%
Flanders/ Belgium	14.7%	35.3%	13.7%	23.5%	12.7%
Galilee/ Israel	37.5%	54.2%	4.2%	0.0%	4.2%
Apulia/ Italy	25.0%	53.6%	17.9%	17.9%	3.6%
North Macedonia	18.1%	28.4%	19.0%	30.2%	4.3%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	14.7%	35.3%	13.7%	23.5%	12.7%

¹⁷ The the out of the tables is maintained throughout the Annex

	12.7%	29.5%	17.8%	29.0%	11.0%
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PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services					
	There is enough support for teleworking opportunities in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	8.28%	23.57%	41.40%	16.56%	1.27%	8.92%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.68%	48.39%	35.48%	6.45%	0.00%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	4.44%	13.33%	13.33%	33.33%	21.11%	14.44%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	9.11%	27.79%	30.07%	16.40%	4.56%	12.07%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.00%	9.21%	22.37%	39.47%	23.68%	5.26%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	9.76%	31.71%	19.51%	12.20%	9.76%	17.07%
Cuenca/ Spain	61.02%	27.12%	3.39%	1.69%	0.00%	6.78%
Flanders/ Belgium	4.00%	7.00%	26.00%	30.00%	25.00%	8.00%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	29.17%	37.50%	20.83%	8.33%	4.17%
Apulia/ Italy	6.90%	34.48%	17.24%	24.14%	10.34%	17.24%
North Macedonia	10.08%	32.77%	30.25%	20.17%	2.52%	4.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	4.00%	7.00%	26.00%	30.00%	25.00%	8.00%
	9.64%	23.08%	27.59%	20.71%	9.33%	9.64%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services				
	There is enough support for teleworking opportunities in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	9.1%	25.9%	45.5%	18.2%	1.4%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.7%	48.4%	35.5%	6.5%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	5.2%	15.6%	15.6%	39.0%	24.7%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	10.4%	31.6%	34.2%	18.7%	5.2%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.0%	9.7%	23.6%	41.7%	25.0%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	11.8%	38.2%	23.5%	14.7%	11.8%
Cuenca/ Spain	65.5%	29.1%	3.6%	1.8%	0.0%
Flanders/ Belgium	4.3%	7.6%	28.3%	32.6%	27.2%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	30.4%	39.1%	21.7%	8.7%
Apulia/ Italy	8.3%	41.7%	20.8%	29.2%	12.5%
North Macedonia	10.5%	34.2%	31.6%	21.1%	2.6%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	4.3%	7.6%	28.3%	32.6%	27.2%
	10.7%	25.5%	30.5%	22.9%	10.3%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services					
	There are good daycare facilities in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	4.46%	15.29%	19.75%	48.41%	10.19%	1.91%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.45%	48.39%	19.35%	19.35%	0.00%	6.45%
Hame/ Finland	4.44%	6.67%	16.67%	21.11%	20.00%	31.11%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	8.43%	22.55%	28.25%	19.59%	4.56%	16.63%
Monaghan/ Ireland	12.99%	29.87%	16.88%	27.27%	7.79%	5.19%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	4.88%	9.76%	14.63%	53.66%	17.07%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	49.09%	30.91%	5.45%	10.91%	1.82%	1.82%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	1.98%	13.86%	38.61%	33.66%	11.88%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	12.50%	29.17%	37.50%	12.50%	8.33%
Apulia/ Italy	3.33%	20.00%	26.67%	43.33%	6.67%	3.33%
North Macedonia	19.33%	42.02%	13.45%	22.69%	0.84%	1.68%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	1.98%	13.86%	38.61%	33.66%	11.88%
	8.85%	19.84%	20.32%	28.70%	11.23%	11.07%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services				
	There are good daycare facilities in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	4.5%	15.6%	20.1%	49.4%	10.4%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.9%	51.7%	20.7%	20.7%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	6.5%	9.7%	24.2%	30.6%	29.0%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	10.1%	27.0%	33.9%	23.5%	5.5%
Monaghan/ Ireland	13.7%	31.5%	17.8%	28.8%	8.2%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	4.9%	9.8%	14.6%	53.7%	17.1%
Cuenca/ Spain	50.0%	31.5%	5.6%	11.1%	1.9%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	2.2%	15.7%	43.8%	38.2%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	13.6%	31.8%	40.9%	13.6%
Apulia/ Italy	3.4%	20.7%	27.6%	44.8%	6.9%
North Macedonia	19.7%	42.7%	13.7%	23.1%	0.9%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	2.2%	15.7%	43.8%	38.2%
	10.0%	22.3%	22.8%	32.3%	12.6%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services					
	The mobility possibilities to the main city in the region are sufficient					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	8.28%	21.02%	20.38%	39.49%	9.55%	1.27%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	25.81%	35.48%	32.26%	6.45%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	31.11%	36.67%	12.22%	12.22%	6.67%	1.11%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	13.44%	31.66%	15.03%	23.69%	9.11%	7.06%
Monaghan/ Ireland	1.28%	15.38%	14.10%	46.15%	20.51%	2.56%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	7.32%	14.63%	7.32%	43.90%	24.39%	2.44%
Cuenca/ Spain	15.52%	37.93%	17.24%	24.14%	1.72%	3.45%
Flanders/ Belgium	11.65%	27.18%	9.71%	33.98%	16.50%	0.97%
Galilee/ Israel	24.00%	44.00%	24.00%	8.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.33%	56.67%	26.67%	3.33%	3.33%	6.67%
North Macedonia	8.40%	19.33%	18.49%	47.06%	5.88%	0.84%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	11.65%	27.18%	9.71%	33.98%	16.50%	0.97%
	12.09%	28.26%	15.70%	30.14%	10.36%	3.45%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services				
	The mobility possibilities to the main city in the region are sufficient				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	8.4%	21.3%	20.6%	40.0%	9.7%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	25.8%	35.5%	32.3%	6.5%
Hame/ Finland	31.5%	37.1%	12.4%	12.4%	6.7%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	14.5%	34.1%	16.2%	25.5%	9.8%
Monaghan/ Ireland	1.3%	15.8%	14.5%	47.4%	21.1%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	7.5%	15.0%	7.5%	45.0%	25.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	16.1%	39.3%	17.9%	25.0%	1.8%
Flanders/ Belgium	11.8%	27.5%	9.8%	34.3%	16.7%
Galilee/ Israel	24.0%	44.0%	24.0%	8.0%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	3.6%	60.7%	28.6%	3.6%	3.6%
North Macedonia	8.5%	19.5%	18.6%	47.5%	5.9%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	11.8%	27.5%	9.8%	34.3%	16.7%
	12.5%	29.3%	16.3%	31.2%	10.7%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities					
	I feel that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area.					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	3.18%	28.03%	18.47%	36.94%	12.74%	0.64%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.23%	22.58%	45.16%	29.03%	0.00%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	2.22%	16.67%	23.33%	40.00%	17.78%	0.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.82%	17.08%	14.35%	44.65%	21.87%	0.23%
Monaghan/ Ireland	11.54%	34.62%	15.38%	32.05%	6.41%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	7.32%	12.20%	19.51%	41.46%	17.07%	2.44%
Cuenca/ Spain	38.18%	32.73%	18.18%	10.91%	0.00%	0.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.94%	9.71%	16.50%	39.81%	32.04%	0.00%
Galilee/ Israel	4.00%	40.00%	12.00%	32.00%	12.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	10.00%	26.67%	13.33%	26.67%	10.00%	13.33%
North Macedonia	19.33%	40.34%	21.85%	15.13%	0.84%	2.52%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.94%	9.71%	16.50%	39.81%	32.04%	0.00%
	6.29%	21.79%	17.62%	36.43%	17.07%	0.79%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities				
	I feel that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area.				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	3.2%	28.2%	18.6%	37.2%	12.8%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.2%	22.6%	45.2%	29.0%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	2.2%	16.7%	23.3%	40.0%	17.8%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.8%	17.1%	14.4%	44.7%	21.9%
Monaghan/ Ireland	11.5%	34.6%	15.4%	32.1%	6.4%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	7.5%	12.5%	20.0%	42.5%	17.5%
Cuenca/ Spain	38.2%	32.7%	18.2%	10.9%	0.0%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.9%	9.7%	16.5%	39.8%	32.0%
Galilee/ Israel	4.0%	40.0%	12.0%	32.0%	12.0%
Apulia/ Italy	11.5%	30.8%	15.4%	30.8%	11.5%
North Macedonia	19.8%	41.4%	22.4%	15.5%	0.9%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.9%	9.7%	16.5%	39.8%	32.0%
	6.3%	22.0%	17.8%	36.7%	17.2%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities					
	There are enough and well provided spaces to allow young people to meet					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	7.01%	40.76%	26.11%	21.02%	4.46%	0.64%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.45%	9.68%	38.71%	41.94%	3.23%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	14.44%	30.00%	18.89%	18.89%	3.33%	14.44%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	5.01%	35.76%	23.69%	25.51%	5.47%	4.56%
Monaghan/ Ireland	2.60%	14.29%	9.09%	46.75%	27.27%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	14.63%	19.51%	26.83%	26.83%	9.76%	2.44%
Cuenca/ Spain	32.73%	32.73%	21.82%	9.09%	1.82%	1.82%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	14.71%	28.43%	33.33%	17.65%	5.88%
Galilee/ Israel	20.00%	20.00%	32.00%	16.00%	4.00%	8.00%
Apulia/ Italy	10.00%	13.33%	30.00%	23.33%	13.33%	10.00%
North Macedonia	37.82%	35.29%	16.81%	6.72%	0.84%	2.52%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	14.71%	28.43%	33.33%	17.65%	5.88%
	10.02%	29.10%	23.58%	24.76%	8.12%	4.42%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities				
	There are enough and well provided spaces to allow young people to meet				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	7.1%	41.0%	26.3%	21.2%	4.5%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.5%	9.7%	38.7%	41.9%	3.2%
Hame/ Finland	16.9%	35.1%	22.1%	22.1%	3.9%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	5.3%	37.5%	24.8%	26.7%	5.7%
Monaghan/ Ireland	2.6%	14.3%	9.1%	46.8%	27.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	15.0%	20.0%	27.5%	27.5%	10.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	33.3%	33.3%	22.2%	9.3%	1.9%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	15.6%	30.2%	35.4%	18.8%
Galilee/ Israel	21.7%	21.7%	34.8%	17.4%	4.3%
Apulia/ Italy	11.1%	14.8%	33.3%	25.9%	14.8%
North Macedonia	38.8%	36.2%	17.2%	6.9%	0.9%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	15.6%	30.2%	35.4%	18.8%
	10.5%	30.4%	24.7%	25.9%	8.5%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living					
	Housing opportunities are adequate in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	3.82%	22.93%	24.20%	41.40%	7.01%	0.64%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	9.68%	61.29%	25.81%	0.00%	3.23%
Hame/ Finland	2.22%	17.78%	14.44%	35.56%	25.56%	4.44%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	21.64%	44.19%	12.98%	17.31%	1.59%	2.28%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.00%	25.97%	18.18%	32.47%	20.78%	2.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	4.88%	14.63%	17.07%	60.98%	2.44%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	6.98%	12.79%	19.77%	17.44%	5.81%	37.21%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.97%	4.85%	9.71%	60.19%	24.27%	0.00%
Galilee/ Israel	4.17%	12.50%	25.00%	45.83%	12.50%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	6.67%	10.00%	20.00%	26.67%	13.33%	23.33%
North Macedonia	5.04%	17.65%	26.89%	44.54%	2.52%	3.36%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.97%	4.85%	9.71%	60.19%	24.27%	0.00%
	9.38%	24.85%	17.62%	34.00%	9.46%	4.69%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living				
	Housing opportunities are adequate in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	3.8%	23.1%	24.4%	41.7%	7.1%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	10.0%	63.3%	26.7%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	2.3%	18.6%	15.1%	37.2%	26.7%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	22.1%	45.2%	13.3%	17.7%	1.6%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.0%	26.7%	18.7%	33.3%	21.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	4.9%	14.6%	17.1%	61.0%	2.4%
Cuenca/ Spain	11.1%	20.4%	31.5%	27.8%	9.3%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.0%	4.9%	9.7%	60.2%	24.3%
Galilee/ Israel	4.2%	12.5%	25.0%	45.8%	12.5%
Apulia/ Italy	8.7%	13.0%	26.1%	34.8%	17.4%
North Macedonia	5.2%	18.3%	27.8%	46.1%	2.6%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.0%	4.9%	9.7%	60.2%	24.3%
	9.8%	26.1%	18.5%	35.7%	9.9%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living					
	There are problems of integration with some population in the territory (Minorities, new comers....).					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	1.91%	17.20%	29.30%	32.48%	16.56%	2.55%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.23%	29.03%	25.81%	22.58%	19.35%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	3.33%	23.33%	37.78%	23.33%	5.56%	6.67%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	4.33%	22.78%	34.62%	18.45%	5.69%	14.12%
Monaghan/ Ireland	18.67%	54.67%	14.67%	6.67%	2.67%	2.67%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	9.76%	39.02%	26.83%	14.63%	4.88%	4.88%
Cuenca/ Spain	25.93%	29.63%	22.22%	9.26%	7.41%	5.56%
Flanders/ Belgium	8.74%	28.16%	39.81%	18.45%	1.94%	2.91%
Galilee/ Israel	4.17%	8.33%	33.33%	41.67%	8.33%	4.17%
Apulia/ Italy	3.33%	20.00%	26.67%	36.67%	3.33%	10.00%
North Macedonia	8.40%	33.61%	28.57%	21.01%	3.36%	5.04%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	8.74%	28.16%	39.81%	18.45%	1.94%	2.91%
	6.95%	26.54%	32.07%	20.54%	6.40%	7.50%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living				
	There are problems of integration with some population in the territory (Minorities, new comers....).				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	2.0%	17.6%	30.1%	33.3%	17.0%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.2%	29.0%	25.8%	22.6%	19.4%
Hame/ Finland	3.6%	25.0%	40.5%	25.0%	6.0%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	5.0%	26.5%	40.3%	21.5%	6.6%
Monaghan/ Ireland	19.2%	56.2%	15.1%	6.8%	2.7%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	10.3%	41.0%	28.2%	15.4%	5.1%
Cuenca/ Spain	27.5%	31.4%	23.5%	9.8%	7.8%
Flanders/ Belgium	9.0%	29.0%	41.0%	19.0%	2.0%
Galilee/ Israel	4.3%	8.7%	34.8%	43.5%	8.7%
Apulia/ Italy	3.7%	22.2%	29.6%	40.7%	3.7%
North Macedonia	8.8%	35.4%	30.1%	22.1%	3.5%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	9.0%	29.0%	41.0%	19.0%	2.0%
	7.5%	28.7%	34.7%	22.2%	6.9%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital					
	There are enough young people in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	1.27%	19.11%	19.11%	50.96%	8.92%	0.64%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	19.35%	41.94%	35.48%	3.23%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	16.67%	40.00%	17.78%	20.00%	3.33%	2.22%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	11.85%	39.18%	17.31%	27.33%	3.64%	0.68%
Monaghan/ Ireland	10.26%	44.87%	20.51%	21.79%	2.56%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	0.00%	12.20%	51.22%	36.59%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	50.85%	28.81%	10.17%	3.39%	1.69%	5.08%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	8.91%	19.80%	52.48%	17.82%	0.99%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	48.00%	16.00%	36.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	10.34%	27.59%	13.79%	37.93%	10.34%	10.34%
North Macedonia	25.21%	43.70%	9.24%	15.97%	4.20%	1.68%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	8.91%	19.80%	52.48%	17.82%	0.99%
	11.02%	30.39%	17.40%	32.60%	7.32%	1.26%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital				
	There are enough young people in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	1.3%	19.2%	19.2%	51.3%	9.0%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	19.4%	41.9%	35.5%	3.2%
Hame/ Finland	17.0%	40.9%	18.2%	20.5%	3.4%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	11.9%	39.4%	17.4%	27.5%	3.7%
Monaghan/ Ireland	10.3%	44.9%	20.5%	21.8%	2.6%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	0.0%	12.2%	51.2%	36.6%
Cuenca/ Spain	53.6%	30.4%	10.7%	3.6%	1.8%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	9.0%	20.0%	53.0%	18.0%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	48.0%	16.0%	36.0%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	11.5%	30.8%	15.4%	42.3%	11.5%
North Macedonia	25.6%	44.4%	9.4%	16.2%	4.3%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	9.0%	20.0%	53.0%	18.0%
	11.2%	30.8%	17.6%	33.0%	7.4%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital					
	There are enough babies born in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	3.18%	22.93%	32.48%	33.76%	7.01%	0.64%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	58.06%	19.35%	19.35%	3.23%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	16.67%	46.67%	24.44%	5.56%	0.00%	6.67%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	15.26%	42.37%	18.22%	18.68%	4.56%	0.91%
Monaghan/ Ireland	11.69%	53.25%	25.97%	6.49%	1.30%	1.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.44%	9.76%	7.32%	43.90%	31.71%	4.88%
Cuenca/ Spain	56.90%	32.76%	3.45%	3.45%	0.00%	3.45%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	2.94%	27.45%	48.04%	18.63%	2.94%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	16.67%	29.17%	50.00%	0.00%	4.17%
Apulia/ Italy	6.90%	13.79%	37.93%	31.03%	3.45%	6.90%
North Macedonia	18.49%	47.06%	14.29%	12.61%	2.52%	5.04%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	2.94%	27.45%	48.04%	18.63%	2.94%
	12.14%	32.78%	21.67%	24.03%	6.93%	2.44%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital				
	There are enough babies born in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	3.2%	23.1%	32.7%	34.0%	7.1%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	58.1%	19.4%	19.4%	3.2%
Hame/ Finland	17.9%	50.0%	26.2%	6.0%	0.0%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	15.4%	42.8%	18.4%	18.9%	4.6%
Monaghan/ Ireland	11.8%	53.9%	26.3%	6.6%	1.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.6%	10.3%	7.7%	46.2%	33.3%
Cuenca/ Spain	58.9%	33.9%	3.6%	3.6%	0.0%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	3.0%	28.3%	49.5%	19.2%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	17.4%	30.4%	52.2%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	7.4%	14.8%	40.7%	33.3%	3.7%
North Macedonia	19.5%	49.6%	15.0%	13.3%	2.7%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	3.0%	28.3%	49.5%	19.2%
	12.4%	33.6%	22.2%	24.6%	7.1%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital					
	It is possible to find opportunities to develop family plans.					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	0.64%	11.46%	36.94%	45.86%	3.82%	1.27%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.23%	19.35%	54.84%	22.58%	0.00%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	3.33%	5.56%	22.22%	17.78%	5.56%	45.56%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	6.38%	20.96%	31.21%	33.03%	5.92%	2.51%
Monaghan/ Ireland	5.19%	33.77%	24.68%	28.57%	5.19%	2.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	25.00%	27.50%	32.50%	5.00%	10.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	27.12%	35.59%	11.86%	11.86%	5.08%	8.47%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	5.88%	18.63%	48.04%	20.59%	6.86%
Galilee/ Israel	4.00%	28.00%	36.00%	24.00%	4.00%	4.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	17.24%	37.93%	31.03%	3.45%	6.90%
North Macedonia	11.76%	31.09%	31.09%	19.33%	1.68%	5.04%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	5.88%	18.63%	48.04%	20.59%	6.86%
	5.43%	18.82%	28.66%	32.91%	7.24%	6.93%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital				
	It is possible to find opportunities to develop family plans.				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	0.6%	11.6%	37.4%	46.5%	3.9%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.2%	19.4%	54.8%	22.6%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	6.1%	10.2%	40.8%	32.7%	10.2%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	6.5%	21.5%	32.0%	33.9%	6.1%
Monaghan/ Ireland	5.3%	34.7%	25.3%	29.3%	5.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	27.8%	30.6%	36.1%	5.6%
Cuenca/ Spain	29.6%	38.9%	13.0%	13.0%	5.6%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	6.3%	20.0%	51.6%	22.1%
Galilee/ Israel	4.2%	29.2%	37.5%	25.0%	4.2%
Apulia/ Italy	3.7%	18.5%	40.7%	33.3%	3.7%
North Macedonia	12.4%	32.7%	32.7%	20.4%	1.8%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	6.3%	20.0%	51.6%	22.1%
	5.8%	20.2%	30.8%	35.4%	7.8%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation					
	The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses.					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	6.37%	30.57%	33.76%	24.20%	1.27%	3.82%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.45%	51.61%	29.03%	12.90%	0.00%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	3.37%	10.11%	30.34%	35.96%	3.37%	16.85%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	8.43%	22.32%	28.25%	29.84%	5.24%	5.92%
Monaghan/ Ireland	2.60%	48.05%	23.38%	18.18%	5.19%	2.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	24.39%	29.27%	9.76%	9.76%	0.00%	26.83%
Cuenca/ Spain	30.51%	28.81%	8.47%	16.95%	8.47%	6.78%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	15.53%	19.42%	40.78%	18.45%	5.83%
Galilee/ Israel	12.00%	52.00%	20.00%	16.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	13.79%	41.38%	31.03%	3.45%	6.90%
North Macedonia	5.88%	26.05%	24.37%	40.34%	1.68%	1.68%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	15.53%	19.42%	40.78%	18.45%	5.83%
	7.31%	24.92%	25.63%	29.72%	6.13%	6.29%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation				
	The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses.				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	6.6%	31.8%	35.1%	25.2%	1.3%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.5%	51.6%	29.0%	12.9%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	4.1%	12.2%	36.5%	43.2%	4.1%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	9.0%	23.7%	30.0%	31.7%	5.6%
Monaghan/ Ireland	2.7%	49.3%	24.0%	18.7%	5.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	33.3%	40.0%	13.3%	13.3%	0.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	32.7%	30.9%	9.1%	18.2%	9.1%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	16.5%	20.6%	43.3%	19.6%
Galilee/ Israel	12.0%	52.0%	20.0%	16.0%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	3.7%	14.8%	44.4%	33.3%	3.7%
North Macedonia	6.0%	26.5%	24.8%	41.0%	1.7%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	16.5%	20.6%	43.3%	19.6%
	7.8%	26.6%	27.3%	31.7%	6.5%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation					
	There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	10.83%	30.57%	38.85%	16.56%	1.27%	1.91%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.45%	19.35%	58.06%	16.13%	0.00%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	1.14%	14.77%	27.27%	32.95%	10.23%	13.64%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	6.15%	20.73%	32.57%	28.70%	5.01%	6.83%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.00%	50.65%	18.18%	24.68%	3.90%	2.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	14.63%	31.71%	21.95%	19.51%	0.00%	12.20%
Cuenca/ Spain	35.09%	26.32%	24.56%	5.26%	7.02%	1.75%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	10.68%	30.10%	36.89%	10.68%	11.65%
Galilee/ Israel	12.00%	44.00%	20.00%	16.00%	0.00%	8.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.57%	14.29%	21.43%	25.00%	14.29%	21.43%
North Macedonia	8.40%	28.57%	31.09%	28.57%	0.00%	3.36%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	10.68%	30.10%	36.89%	10.68%	11.65%
	6.86%	23.34%	30.99%	26.58%	5.21%	7.02%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation				
	There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	11.0%	31.2%	39.6%	16.9%	1.3%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.5%	19.4%	58.1%	16.1%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	1.3%	17.1%	31.6%	38.2%	11.8%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	6.6%	22.2%	35.0%	30.8%	5.4%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.0%	52.0%	18.7%	25.3%	4.0%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	16.7%	36.1%	25.0%	22.2%	0.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	35.7%	26.8%	25.0%	5.4%	7.1%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	12.1%	34.1%	41.8%	12.1%
Galilee/ Israel	13.0%	47.8%	21.7%	17.4%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	4.5%	18.2%	27.3%	31.8%	18.2%
North Macedonia	8.7%	29.6%	32.2%	29.6%	0.0%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	12.1%	34.1%	41.8%	12.1%
	7.4%	25.1%	33.3%	28.6%	5.6%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation					
	There are adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development with the provision of experienced services					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	11.46%	28.66%	36.31%	18.47%	1.27%	3.82%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.68%	48.39%	35.48%	6.45%	0.00%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	4.49%	12.36%	33.71%	32.58%	4.49%	12.36%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	10.02%	30.30%	32.80%	15.26%	2.96%	8.66%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.00%	40.79%	23.68%	21.05%	7.89%	6.58%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	26.83%	36.59%	4.88%	7.32%	0.00%	24.39%
Cuenca/ Spain	33.78%	24.32%	8.11%	5.41%	4.05%	24.32%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.98%	11.76%	41.18%	24.51%	7.84%	13.73%
Galilee/ Israel	4.00%	48.00%	16.00%	24.00%	0.00%	8.00%
Apulia/ Italy	6.90%	10.34%	41.38%	31.03%	10.34%	41.38%
North Macedonia	8.40%	40.34%	32.77%	15.13%	0.84%	2.52%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.98%	11.76%	41.18%	24.51%	7.84%	13.73%
	9.35%	27.65%	31.70%	18.15%	3.74%	9.42%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation				
	There are adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development with the provision of experienced services				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	11.9%	29.8%	37.7%	19.2%	1.3%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.7%	48.4%	35.5%	6.5%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	5.1%	14.1%	38.5%	37.2%	5.1%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	11.0%	33.2%	35.9%	16.7%	3.2%
Monaghan/ Ireland	0.0%	43.7%	25.4%	22.5%	8.5%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	35.5%	48.4%	6.5%	9.7%	0.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	44.6%	32.1%	10.7%	7.1%	5.4%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.1%	13.6%	47.7%	28.4%	9.1%
Galilee/ Israel	4.3%	52.2%	17.4%	26.1%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	6.9%	10.3%	41.4%	31.0%	10.3%
North Macedonia	8.6%	41.4%	33.6%	15.5%	0.9%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.1%	13.6%	47.7%	28.4%	9.1%
	10.3%	30.5%	35.0%	20.0%	4.1%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation					
	There are enough possibilities for employment					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	10.19%	28.66%	23.57%	33.12%	4.46%	0.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.68%	54.84%	32.26%	3.23%	0.00%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	16.67%	43.33%	23.33%	12.22%	2.22%	2.22%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	19.59%	41.69%	16.63%	18.68%	2.05%	1.37%
Monaghan/ Ireland	1.30%	28.57%	14.29%	41.56%	14.29%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	9.76%	31.71%	14.63%	31.71%	12.20%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	25.00%	27.94%	16.18%	8.82%	2.94%	19.12%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.99%	11.88%	23.76%	43.56%	16.83%	2.97%
Galilee/ Israel	44.00%	48.00%	4.00%	4.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%
North Macedonia	9.24%	31.09%	31.09%	21.85%	5.04%	1.68%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.99%	11.88%	23.76%	43.56%	16.83%	2.97%
	13.29%	32.91%	20.42%	24.98%	6.08%	2.32%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation				
	There are enough possibilities for employment				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	10.2%	28.7%	23.6%	33.1%	4.5%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.7%	54.8%	32.3%	3.2%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	17.0%	44.3%	23.9%	12.5%	2.3%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	19.9%	42.3%	16.9%	18.9%	2.1%
Monaghan/ Ireland	1.3%	28.6%	14.3%	41.6%	14.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	9.8%	31.7%	14.6%	31.7%	12.2%
Cuenca/ Spain	30.9%	34.5%	20.0%	10.9%	3.6%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.0%	12.2%	24.5%	44.9%	17.3%
Galilee/ Israel	44.0%	48.0%	4.0%	4.0%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
North Macedonia	9.4%	31.6%	31.6%	22.2%	5.1%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.0%	12.2%	24.5%	44.9%	17.3%
	13.6%	33.7%	20.9%	25.6%	6.2%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation					
	The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	3.82%	14.65%	31.21%	36.31%	13.38%	0.64%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	9.68%	22.58%	58.06%	9.68%	100.00%
Hame/ Finland	1.11%	2.22%	7.78%	47.78%	34.44%	6.67%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.82%	7.06%	13.44%	55.13%	17.54%	5.01%
Monaghan/ Ireland	14.10%	39.74%	32.05%	10.26%	1.28%	2.56%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	7.32%	21.95%	39.02%	17.07%	14.63%
Cuenca/ Spain	1.49%	5.97%	5.97%	34.33%	34.33%	17.91%
Flanders/ Belgium	11.65%	12.62%	16.50%	36.89%	18.45%	3.88%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	4.00%	24.00%	52.00%	16.00%	4.00%
Apulia/ Italy	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%
North Macedonia	3.36%	20.17%	20.17%	47.90%	5.88%	2.52%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	11.65%	12.62%	16.50%	36.89%	18.45%	3.88%
	4.39%	11.81%	17.88%	44.13%	16.92%	4.87%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation				
	The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	3.8%	14.7%	31.4%	36.5%	13.5%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	9.7%	22.6%	58.1%	9.7%
Hame/ Finland	1.2%	2.4%	8.3%	51.2%	36.9%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.9%	7.4%	14.1%	58.0%	18.5%
Monaghan/ Ireland	14.5%	40.8%	32.9%	10.5%	1.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	8.6%	25.7%	45.7%	20.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	1.8%	7.3%	7.3%	41.8%	41.8%
Flanders/ Belgium	12.1%	13.1%	17.2%	38.4%	19.2%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	4.2%	25.0%	54.2%	16.7%
Apulia/ Italy	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.00%
North Macedonia	3.4%	20.7%	20.7%	49.1%	6.0%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	12.1%	13.1%	17.2%	38.4%	19.2%
	4.6%	12.4%	18.8%	46.4%	17.8%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas					
	Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	1.91%	21.02%	21.66%	45.22%	7.01%	3.18%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	9.68%	29.03%	54.84%	0.00%	6.45%
Hame/ Finland	1.11%	6.67%	14.44%	48.89%	26.67%	2.22%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.73%	16.40%	25.28%	43.51%	9.57%	2.51%
Monaghan/ Ireland	5.26%	46.05%	18.42%	21.05%	7.89%	1.32%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	9.76%	14.63%	46.34%	17.07%	12.20%
Cuenca/ Spain	3.45%	24.14%	18.97%	29.31%	20.69%	3.45%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.94%	19.42%	21.36%	45.63%	9.71%	1.94%
Galilee/ Israel	4.00%	32.00%	16.00%	48.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	13.79%	34.48%	13.79%	13.79%	20.69%
North Macedonia	9.24%	17.65%	24.37%	42.02%	2.52%	4.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.94%	19.42%	21.36%	45.63%	9.71%	1.94%
	3.07%	18.88%	22.42%	42.09%	10.15%	3.38%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas				
	Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	2.0%	21.7%	22.4%	46.7%	7.2%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	10.3%	31.0%	58.6%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	1.1%	6.8%	14.8%	50.0%	27.3%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.8%	16.8%	25.9%	44.6%	9.8%
Monaghan/ Ireland	5.3%	46.7%	18.7%	21.3%	8.0%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	11.1%	16.7%	52.8%	19.4%
Cuenca/ Spain	3.6%	25.0%	19.6%	30.4%	21.4%
Flanders/ Belgium	2.0%	19.8%	21.8%	46.5%	9.9%
Galilee/ Israel	4.0%	32.0%	16.0%	48.0%	0.0%
Apulia/ Italy	4.3%	17.4%	43.5%	17.4%	17.4%
North Macedonia	9.6%	18.4%	25.4%	43.9%	2.6%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	2.0%	19.8%	21.8%	46.5%	9.9%
	3.2%	19.5%	23.2%	43.6%	10.5%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas					
	Loneliness and isolation do not affect many people in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	3.82%	23.57%	31.21%	34.39%	1.91%	5.10%
Central Greece/ Greece	16.13%	22.58%	19.35%	35.48%	0.00%	6.45%
Hame/ Finland	5.56%	46.67%	25.56%	13.33%	0.00%	8.89%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	9.11%	41.23%	31.21%	11.85%	1.59%	5.01%
Monaghan/ Ireland	3.90%	5.19%	5.19%	59.74%	25.97%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	9.76%	24.39%	53.66%	9.76%	2.44%
Cuenca/ Spain	19.35%	30.65%	17.74%	19.35%	3.23%	9.68%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.97%	34.95%	25.24%	27.18%	7.77%	3.88%
Galilee/ Israel	4.00%	40.00%	20.00%	28.00%	4.00%	4.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	17.24%	17.24%	34.48%	17.24%	10.34%
North Macedonia	15.97%	31.93%	21.01%	22.69%	2.52%	5.88%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.97%	34.95%	25.24%	27.18%	7.77%	3.88%
	7.37%	32.84%	25.63%	24.22%	4.78%	5.17%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas				
	Loneliness and isolation do not affect many people in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	4.0%	24.8%	32.9%	36.2%	2.0%
Central Greece/ Greece	17.2%	24.1%	20.7%	37.9%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	6.1%	51.2%	28.0%	14.6%	0.0%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	9.6%	43.4%	32.9%	12.5%	1.7%
Monaghan/ Ireland	3.9%	5.2%	5.2%	59.7%	26.0%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	10.0%	25.0%	55.0%	10.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	21.4%	33.9%	19.6%	21.4%	3.6%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.0%	36.4%	26.3%	28.3%	8.1%
Galilee/ Israel	4.2%	41.7%	20.8%	29.2%	4.2%
Apulia/ Italy	3.8%	19.2%	19.2%	38.5%	19.2%
North Macedonia	17.0%	33.9%	22.3%	24.1%	2.7%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.0%	36.4%	26.3%	28.3%	8.1%
	7.8%	34.6%	27.0%	25.5%	5.0%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas					
	In the area exists lively communities and citizen-driven local activities					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	2.55%	19.11%	26.75%	43.95%	6.37%	1.27%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.23%	45.16%	25.81%	16.13%	0.00%	9.68%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	7.78%	20.00%	50.00%	20.00%	2.22%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	3.87%	16.63%	32.80%	40.09%	4.78%	1.82%
Monaghan/ Ireland	10.53%	50.00%	19.74%	17.11%	2.63%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.44%	12.20%	17.07%	56.10%	12.20%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	9.84%	36.07%	18.03%	19.67%	6.56%	9.84%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	11.65%	26.21%	48.54%	13.59%	0.00%
Galilee/ Israel	4.17%	8.33%	29.17%	45.83%	12.50%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	17.24%	20.69%	55.17%	3.45%	3.45%
North Macedonia	17.65%	41.18%	29.41%	8.40%	1.68%	1.68%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	11.65%	26.21%	48.54%	13.59%	0.00%
	4.71%	21.13%	27.26%	37.71%	7.31%	1.89%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas				
	In the area exists lively communities and citizen-driven local activities				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	2.6%	19.4%	27.1%	44.5%	6.5%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.6%	50.0%	28.6%	17.9%	0.0%
Hame/ Finland	0.0%	8.0%	20.5%	51.1%	20.5%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	3.9%	16.9%	33.4%	40.8%	4.9%
Monaghan/ Ireland	10.5%	50.0%	19.7%	17.1%	2.6%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.4%	12.2%	17.1%	56.1%	12.2%
Cuenca/ Spain	10.9%	40.0%	20.0%	21.8%	7.3%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	11.7%	26.2%	48.5%	13.6%
Galilee/ Israel	4.2%	8.3%	29.2%	45.8%	12.5%
Apulia/ Italy	3.6%	17.9%	21.4%	57.1%	3.6%
North Macedonia	17.9%	41.9%	29.9%	8.5%	1.7%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	11.7%	26.2%	48.5%	13.6%
	4.8%	21.5%	27.8%	38.4%	7.4%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas					
	There are good opportunities for women to participate in various social activities and working life in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	1.91%	12.10%	35.67%	42.68%	5.10%	2.55%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.45%	6.45%	29.03%	45.16%	3.23%	9.68%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	5.56%	13.33%	51.11%	25.56%	4.44%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.51%	10.25%	20.50%	51.71%	13.44%	1.59%
Monaghan/ Ireland	8.97%	57.69%	15.38%	12.82%	2.56%	2.56%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	2.44%	12.20%	60.98%	24.39%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	6.25%	15.00%	21.25%	20.00%	7.50%	30.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	1.94%	16.50%	60.19%	21.36%	0.00%
Galilee/ Israel	4.00%	20.00%	32.00%	32.00%	8.00%	4.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.57%	10.71%	25.00%	53.57%	7.14%	3.57%
North Macedonia	7.56%	29.41%	19.33%	36.13%	4.20%	3.36%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	1.94%	16.50%	60.19%	21.36%	0.00%
	2.94%	13.60%	21.10%	45.98%	12.52%	3.86%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas				
	There are good opportunities for women to participate in various social activities and working life in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	2.0%	12.4%	36.6%	43.8%	5.2%
Central Greece/ Greece	7.1%	7.1%	32.1%	50.0%	3.6%
Hame/ Finland	0.0%	5.8%	14.0%	53.5%	26.7%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.5%	10.4%	20.8%	52.5%	13.7%
Monaghan/ Ireland	9.2%	59.2%	15.8%	13.2%	2.6%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	2.4%	12.2%	61.0%	24.4%
Cuenca/ Spain	8.9%	21.4%	30.4%	28.6%	10.7%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	1.9%	16.5%	60.2%	21.4%
Galilee/ Israel	4.2%	20.8%	33.3%	33.3%	8.3%
Apulia/ Italy	3.7%	11.1%	25.9%	55.6%	7.4%
North Macedonia	7.8%	30.4%	20.0%	37.4%	4.3%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	1.9%	16.5%	60.2%	21.4%
	3.1%	14.1%	21.9%	47.8%	13.0%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity					
	The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	0.64%	3.82%	15.92%	46.50%	33.12%	0.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	3.23%	12.90%	61.29%	22.58%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	1.11%	6.67%	26.67%	65.56%	0.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.37%	1.82%	3.19%	42.82%	50.34%	0.46%
Monaghan/ Ireland	40.26%	48.05%	6.49%	5.19%	0.00%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	4.88%	14.63%	43.90%	36.59%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	5.48%	5.48%	9.59%	23.29%	32.88%	23.29%
Flanders/ Belgium	8.74%	22.33%	12.62%	34.95%	21.36%	0.00%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	0.00%	4.00%	8.00%	88.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	13.79%	17.24%	27.59%	17.24%	24.14%
North Macedonia	0.84%	1.68%	10.08%	57.98%	28.57%	0.84%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	8.74%	22.33%	12.62%	34.95%	21.36%	0.00%
	4.74%	8.62%	8.62%	38.38%	37.53%	2.10%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity				
	The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	0.6%	3.8%	15.9%	46.5%	33.1%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	3.2%	12.9%	61.3%	22.6%
Hame/ Finland	0.0%	1.1%	6.7%	26.7%	65.6%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.4%	1.8%	3.2%	43.0%	50.6%
Monaghan/ Ireland	40.3%	48.1%	6.5%	5.2%	0.0%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	4.9%	14.6%	43.9%	36.6%
Cuenca/ Spain	7.1%	7.1%	12.5%	30.4%	42.9%
Flanders/ Belgium	8.7%	22.3%	12.6%	35.0%	21.4%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	0.0%	4.0%	8.0%	88.0%
Apulia/ Italy	4.5%	18.2%	22.7%	36.4%	22.7%
North Macedonia	0.8%	1.7%	10.2%	58.5%	28.8%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	8.7%	22.3%	12.6%	35.0%	21.4%
	4.8%	8.8%	8.8%	39.2%	38.3%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity					
	Nature in the area is diverse					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	0.00%	7.64%	12.74%	47.77%	31.85%	0.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	19.35%	25.81%	35.48%	19.35%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	1.11%	7.78%	28.89%	62.22%	0.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.37%	2.05%	4.10%	43.96%	48.06%	0.46%
Monaghan/ Ireland	25.33%	54.67%	6.67%	10.67%	1.33%	1.33%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.44%	12.20%	12.20%	39.02%	34.15%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	1.75%	5.26%	15.79%	43.86%	29.82%	3.51%
Flanders/ Belgium	8.91%	22.77%	11.88%	40.59%	14.85%	0.99%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	0.00%	4.00%	12.00%	84.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	3.45%	20.69%	34.48%	17.24%	20.69%
North Macedonia	0.84%	2.52%	10.08%	57.98%	27.73%	0.84%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	8.91%	22.77%	11.88%	40.59%	14.85%	0.99%
	3.72%	10.04%	9.09%	40.95%	35.10%	1.11%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity				
	Nature in the area is diverse				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	0.0%	7.6%	12.7%	47.8%	31.8%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	19.4%	25.8%	35.5%	19.4%
Hame/ Finland	0.0%	1.1%	7.8%	28.9%	62.2%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	1.4%	2.1%	4.1%	44.2%	48.3%
Monaghan/ Ireland	25.7%	55.4%	6.8%	10.8%	1.4%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.4%	12.2%	12.2%	39.0%	34.1%
Cuenca/ Spain	1.8%	5.5%	16.4%	45.5%	30.9%
Flanders/ Belgium	9.0%	23.0%	12.0%	41.0%	15.0%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	0.0%	4.0%	12.0%	84.0%
Apulia/ Italy	4.3%	4.3%	26.1%	43.5%	21.7%
North Macedonia	0.8%	2.5%	10.2%	58.5%	28.0%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	9.0%	23.0%	12.0%	41.0%	15.0%
	3.8%	10.2%	9.2%	41.4%	35.5%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity					
	High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised in the area					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	3.82%	19.11%	38.85%	24.84%	10.19%	3.18%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	9.68%	29.03%	51.61%	9.68%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	2.22%	10.00%	26.67%	24.44%	27.78%	8.89%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.05%	10.25%	25.51%	37.13%	23.01%	2.05%
Monaghan/ Ireland	9.09%	32.47%	16.88%	28.57%	3.90%	9.09%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	9.76%	4.88%	19.51%	24.39%	17.07%	24.39%
Cuenca/ Spain	12.50%	28.13%	25.00%	12.50%	3.13%	18.75%
Flanders/ Belgium	7.92%	11.88%	29.70%	28.71%	18.81%	2.97%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	0.00%	8.00%	20.00%	72.00%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.45%	10.34%	17.24%	48.28%	6.90%	13.79%
North Macedonia	9.24%	30.25%	19.33%	33.61%	5.88%	1.68%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	7.92%	11.88%	29.70%	28.71%	18.81%	2.97%
	5.02%	15.31%	26.14%	31.16%	17.43%	4.95%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity				
	High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised in the area				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	3.9%	19.7%	40.1%	25.7%	10.5%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	9.7%	29.0%	51.6%	9.7%
Hame/ Finland	2.4%	11.0%	29.3%	26.8%	30.5%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.1%	10.5%	26.0%	37.9%	23.5%
Monaghan/ Ireland	10.0%	35.7%	18.6%	31.4%	4.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	12.9%	6.5%	25.8%	32.3%	22.6%
Cuenca/ Spain	15.4%	34.6%	30.8%	15.4%	3.8%
Flanders/ Belgium	8.2%	12.2%	30.6%	29.6%	19.4%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	0.0%	8.0%	20.0%	72.0%
Apulia/ Italy	4.0%	12.0%	20.0%	56.0%	8.0%
North Macedonia	9.4%	30.8%	19.7%	34.2%	6.0%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	8.2%	12.2%	30.6%	29.6%	19.4%
	5.3%	16.1%	27.5%	32.8%	18.3%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity					
	Cultivation practices in the area are done in environmentally sound way					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	8.28%	22.93%	42.68%	20.38%	4.46%	1.27%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.23%	16.13%	54.84%	9.68%	9.68%	6.45%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	8.99%	25.84%	40.45%	20.22%	4.49%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	3.19%	18.00%	30.30%	32.12%	11.16%	5.24%
Monaghan/ Ireland	3.90%	20.78%	31.17%	36.36%	5.19%	2.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	12.50%	47.50%	25.00%	10.00%	5.00%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	4.55%	9.09%	18.18%	15.91%	13.64%	38.64%
Flanders/ Belgium	18.81%	25.74%	30.69%	13.86%	7.92%	2.97%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	12.00%	32.00%	48.00%	4.00%	4.00%
Apulia/ Italy	6.90%	10.34%	41.38%	34.48%	3.45%	3.45%
North Macedonia	7.56%	34.45%	23.53%	27.73%	2.52%	4.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	18.81%	25.74%	30.69%	13.86%	7.92%	2.97%
	6.87%	20.83%	30.86%	26.31%	8.95%	6.17%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity				
	Cultivation practices in the area are done in environmentally sound way				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	8.4%	23.2%	43.2%	20.6%	4.5%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.4%	17.2%	58.6%	10.3%	10.3%
Hame/ Finland	0.0%	9.4%	27.1%	42.4%	21.2%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	3.4%	19.0%	32.0%	33.9%	11.8%
Monaghan/ Ireland	4.0%	21.3%	32.0%	37.3%	5.3%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	12.5%	47.5%	25.0%	10.0%	5.0%
Cuenca/ Spain	7.4%	14.8%	29.6%	25.9%	22.2%
Flanders/ Belgium	19.4%	26.5%	31.6%	14.3%	8.2%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	12.5%	33.3%	50.0%	4.2%
Apulia/ Italy	7.1%	10.7%	42.9%	35.7%	3.6%
North Macedonia	7.9%	36.0%	24.6%	28.9%	2.6%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	19.4%	26.5%	31.6%	14.3%	8.2%
	7.3%	22.2%	32.9%	28.0%	9.5%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity					
	Environment and landscapes are important to me					
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Doesn't apply
Slovakia	0.64%	2.55%	5.73%	26.11%	64.97%	0.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	0.00%	12.90%	48.39%	38.71%	0.00%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	1.12%	1.12%	19.10%	78.65%	0.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.05%	0.23%	2.51%	23.46%	71.30%	0.46%
Monaghan/ Ireland	66.23%	28.57%	2.60%	1.30%	0.00%	1.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	24.39%	75.61%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	3.57%	0.00%	3.57%	32.14%	60.71%	0.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	0.98%	0.98%	14.71%	82.35%	0.98%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	83.33%	0.00%
Apulia/ Italy	3.57%	10.71%	28.57%	32.14%	21.43%	3.57%
North Macedonia	0.00%	2.52%	2.52%	42.02%	52.10%	0.84%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	0.98%	0.98%	14.71%	82.35%	0.98%
	5.06%	2.85%	3.32%	23.56%	64.66%	0.55%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity				
	Environment and landscapes are important to me				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Slovakia	0.6%	2.5%	5.7%	26.1%	65.0%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.0%	0.0%	12.9%	48.4%	38.7%
Hame/ Finland	0.0%	1.1%	1.1%	19.1%	78.7%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.1%	0.2%	2.5%	23.6%	71.6%
Monaghan/ Ireland	67.1%	28.9%	2.6%	1.3%	0.0%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	24.4%	75.6%
Cuenca/ Spain	3.6%	0.0%	3.6%	32.1%	60.7%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.0%	1.0%	1.0%	14.9%	83.2%
Galilee/ Israel	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	16.7%	83.3%
Apulia/ Italy	3.7%	11.1%	29.6%	33.3%	22.2%
North Macedonia	0.0%	2.5%	2.5%	42.4%	52.5%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.0%	1.0%	1.0%	14.9%	83.2%
	5.1%	2.9%	3.3%	23.7%	65.0%

Annex 2: Combined results of PoliRural survey's responses

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There are sufficient public transportation to services (hospital of reference/Specialized health care premises, schools, universities):		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	25.80%	23.20%	51.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	24.10%	51.70%	24.10%
Hame/ Finland	80.70%	4.50%	14.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	34.40%	21.00%	44.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	11.50%	7.70%	80.80%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	37.50%	12.50%	50.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	66.00%	17.90%	16.10%
Flanders/ Belgium	50.00%	13.70%	36.20%
Galilee/ Israel	91.70%	4.20%	4.20%
Apulia/ Italy	78.60%	17.90%	21.50%
North Macedonia	46.50%	19.00%	34.50%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	50.00%	13.70%	36.20%
	42.20%	17.80%	40.00%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	The mobility possibilities to the main city in the region are sufficient		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	29.70%	20.60%	49.70%
Central Greece/ Greece	25.80%	35.50%	38.80%
Hame/ Finland	68.60%	12.40%	19.10%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	48.60%	16.20%	35.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	17.10%	14.50%	68.50%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	22.50%	7.50%	70.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	55.40%	17.90%	26.80%
Flanders/ Belgium	39.30%	9.80%	51.00%
Galilee/ Israel	68.00%	24.00%	8.00%
Apulia/ Italy	64.30%	28.60%	7.20%
North Macedonia	28.00%	18.60%	53.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	39.30%	9.80%	51.00%
	41.80%	16.30%	41.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	The connections between rural and urban areas (e.g. airports, train connection) are sufficient.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	29.70%	20.60%	49.70%
Central Greece/ Greece	25.80%	35.50%	38.80%
Hame/ Finland	68.60%	12.40%	19.10%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	48.60%	16.20%	35.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	17.10%	14.50%	68.50%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	22.50%	7.50%	70.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	55.40%	17.90%	26.80%
Flanders/ Belgium	39.30%	9.80%	51.00%
Galilee/ Israel	68.00%	24.00%	8.00%
Apulia/ Italy	64.30%	28.60%	7.20%
North Macedonia	28.00%	18.60%	53.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	39.30%	9.80%	51.00%
	41.80%	16.30%	41.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	Good intra-regional public transportation is available in the area.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	24.30%	32.10%	43.60%
Central Greece/ Greece	38.70%	25.80%	35.50%
Hame/ Finland	84.10%	10.20%	5.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	46.00%	24.60%	29.40%
Monaghan/ Ireland	10.70%	9.30%	80.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	29.00%	15.80%	55.30%
Cuenca/ Spain	85.70%	7.10%	7.10%
Flanders/ Belgium	49.50%	14.90%	35.60%
Galilee/ Israel	65.20%	26.10%	8.70%
Apulia/ Italy	31.00%	48.30%	27.60%
North Macedonia	37.90%	14.30%	47.90%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	49.50%	14.90%	35.60%
	44.70%	20.60%	34.80%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	Public transportation is important to me		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	14.80%	23.00%	62.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.50%	22.60%	71.00%
Hame/ Finland	23.00%	28.40%	48.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	23.30%	27.10%	49.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	65.20%	19.40%	15.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.50%	25.00%	72.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	1.80%	10.70%	87.50%
Flanders/ Belgium	13.00%	23.00%	64.00%
Galilee/ Israel	17.40%	13.00%	69.60%
Apulia/ Italy	13.70%	41.40%	44.80%
North Macedonia	7.00%	7.00%	86.10%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	13.00%	23.00%	64.00%
	18.80%	22.50%	58.60%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There are good medical (primary care) services in your village /region		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	40.10%	18.50%	41.40%
Central Greece/ Greece	22.60%	48.40%	29.00%
Hame/ Finland	32.20%	17.20%	50.50%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	36.70%	16.70%	46.60%
Monaghan/ Ireland	34.70%	6.70%	58.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	36.60%	22.00%	41.40%
Cuenca/ Spain	43.60%	23.60%	32.70%
Flanders/ Belgium	10.00%	13.00%	77.00%
Galilee/ Israel	79.10%	12.50%	8.30%
Apulia/ Italy	23.30%	40.00%	36.70%
North Macedonia	55.50%	15.10%	29.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	10.00%	13.00%	77.00%
	34.60%	17.40%	48.00%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There are good schools (primary and second level) in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	9.00%	11.50%	79.50%
Central Greece/ Greece	16.20%	16.10%	67.80%
Hame/ Finland	23.80%	12.50%	63.80%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	11.60%	14.20%	74.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	86.50%	9.50%	4.10%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	24.40%	9.80%	65.90%
Cuenca/ Spain	35.20%	14.80%	50.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	14.90%	17.80%	67.30%
Galilee/ Israel	16.70%	29.20%	54.20%
Apulia/ Italy	25.00%	25.00%	50.00%
North Macedonia	36.70%	20.50%	42.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	14.90%	17.80%	67.30%
	21.50%	15.10%	63.50%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There are opportunities for higher or professional education and lifelong learning in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	15.30%	13.50%	71.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	56.60%	23.30%	20.00%
Hame/ Finland	18.00%	10.80%	71.10%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	25.50%	15.90%	58.70%
Monaghan/ Ireland	54.00%	13.20%	32.90%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	53.90%	15.40%	30.70%
Cuenca/ Spain	70.90%	14.50%	14.50%
Flanders/ Belgium	28.20%	12.50%	59.40%
Galilee/ Israel	40.00%	16.00%	44.00%
Apulia/ Italy	24.10%	31.00%	44.80%
North Macedonia	50.80%	17.80%	31.30%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	28.20%	12.50%	59.40%
	32.30%	15.20%	52.50%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There are good daycare facilities in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	20.10%	20.10%	59.80%
Central Greece/ Greece	58.60%	20.70%	20.70%
Hame/ Finland	16.20%	24.20%	59.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	37.10%	33.90%	29.00%
Monaghan/ Ireland	45.20%	17.80%	37.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	14.70%	14.60%	70.80%
Cuenca/ Spain	81.50%	5.60%	13.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	2.20%	15.70%	82.00%
Galilee/ Israel	13.60%	31.80%	54.50%
Apulia/ Italy	24.10%	27.60%	51.70%
North Macedonia	62.40%	13.70%	24.00%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	2.20%	15.70%	82.00%
	32.30%	22.80%	44.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There is a good internet/telecom connectivity (4G/5G/fiber)		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	26.50%	15.50%	58.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.30%	30.00%	66.70%
Hame/ Finland	24.80%	16.90%	58.50%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	23.50%	15.20%	61.40%
Monaghan/ Ireland	37.30%	8.00%	54.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	31.70%	19.50%	48.70%
Cuenca/ Spain	71.50%	12.50%	16.10%
Flanders/ Belgium	4.90%	14.60%	80.60%
Galilee/ Israel	29.20%	16.70%	54.20%
Apulia/ Italy	28.60%	50.00%	46.50%
North Macedonia	13.70%	12.00%	74.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	4.90%	14.60%	80.60%
	22.40%	15.70%	62.00%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There are adequate public provision of online e-health, e-daycare and/or e-learning services		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	31.10%	31.20%	37.60%
Central Greece/ Greece	29.00%	58.10%	12.90%
Hame/ Finland	13.10%	23.80%	41.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	12.30%	33.10%	40.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	7.60%	27.30%	36.40%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	16.10%	32.30%	9.70%
Cuenca/ Spain	35.70%	21.40%	3.60%
Flanders/ Belgium	10.20%	37.50%	30.70%
Galilee/ Israel	41.70%	25.00%	29.20%
Apulia/ Italy	33.30%	47.60%	9.50%
North Macedonia	34.20%	24.60%	27.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	10.20%	37.50%	30.70%
	18.60%	31.80%	32.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	There is enough support for teleworking opportunities in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	35.00%	45.50%	19.60%
Central Greece/ Greece	58.10%	35.50%	6.50%
Hame/ Finland	20.80%	15.60%	63.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	42.00%	34.20%	23.90%
Monaghan/ Ireland	9.70%	23.60%	66.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	50.00%	23.50%	26.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	94.60%	3.60%	1.80%
Flanders/ Belgium	11.90%	28.30%	59.80%
Galilee/ Israel	30.40%	39.10%	30.40%
Apulia/ Italy	50.00%	20.80%	41.70%
North Macedonia	44.70%	31.60%	23.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	11.90%	28.30%	59.80%
	36.20%	30.50%	33.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	1. Availability of public and other services		
	I feel safe and secure in my region		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	23.50%	28.00%	48.40%
Central Greece/ Greece	32.30%	19.40%	48.40%
Hame/ Finland	1.10%	2.20%	96.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	23.20%	25.20%	51.60%
Monaghan/ Ireland	64.90%	16.20%	18.90%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.40%	14.60%	82.90%
Cuenca/ Spain	53.60%	23.20%	23.20%
Flanders/ Belgium	5.00%	3.00%	92.00%
Galilee/ Israel	8.30%	12.50%	79.10%
Apulia/ Italy	16.60%	50.00%	33.40%
North Macedonia	21.10%	19.30%	59.60%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	5.00%	3.00%	92.00%
	21.50%	18.90%	59.60%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities		
	I feel that there are plenty of good and different recreational activities in the area.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	31.40%	18.60%	50.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	25.80%	45.20%	29.00%
Hame/ Finland	18.90%	23.30%	57.80%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	18.90%	14.40%	66.60%
Monaghan/ Ireland	46.10%	15.40%	38.50%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	20.00%	20.00%	60.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	70.90%	18.20%	10.90%
Flanders/ Belgium	11.60%	16.50%	71.80%
Galilee/ Israel	44.00%	12.00%	44.00%
Apulia/ Italy	42.30%	15.40%	42.30%
North Macedonia	61.20%	22.40%	16.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	11.60%	16.50%	71.80%
	28.30%	17.80%	53.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities		
	There are enough recreational activities for young people in the area.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	37.20%	30.10%	32.70%
Central Greece/ Greece	44.80%	20.70%	27.60%
Hame/ Finland	32.90%	25.30%	26.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	26.70%	23.60%	45.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	18.40%	13.20%	61.80%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	25.00%	22.50%	47.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	42.60%	13.00%	0.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	8.10%	18.20%	69.70%
Galilee/ Israel	37.50%	33.30%	20.90%
Apulia/ Italy	8.30%	54.20%	25.00%
North Macedonia	42.20%	19.80%	11.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	8.10%	18.20%	69.70%
	26.70%	22.90%	40.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities		
	There are enough and well provided spaces to allow young people to meet		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	48.10%	26.30%	25.70%
Central Greece/ Greece	16.20%	38.70%	45.10%
Hame/ Finland	52.00%	22.10%	26.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	42.80%	24.80%	32.40%
Monaghan/ Ireland	16.90%	9.10%	74.10%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	35.00%	27.50%	37.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	66.60%	22.20%	11.20%
Flanders/ Belgium	15.60%	30.20%	54.20%
Galilee/ Israel	43.40%	34.80%	21.70%
Apulia/ Italy	25.90%	33.30%	40.70%
North Macedonia	75.00%	17.20%	7.80%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	15.60%	30.20%	54.20%
	40.90%	24.70%	34.40%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities		
	Extra-curricular activities (e.g.: music, dance, arts) for children are accesible in the area.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	16.00%	26.30%	57.70%
Central Greece/ Greece	13.30%	26.70%	60.00%
Hame/ Finland	32.90%	19.70%	47.30%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	12.10%	13.80%	74.00%
Monaghan/ Ireland	54.00%	17.10%	28.90%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	17.50%	10.00%	72.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	64.20%	18.90%	17.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	7.90%	11.90%	80.20%
Galilee/ Israel	21.70%	30.40%	47.80%
Apulia/ Italy	17.80%	35.70%	46.40%
North Macedonia	69.00%	16.40%	14.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	7.90%	11.90%	80.20%
	24.00%	17.10%	58.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities		
	Elderly people are offered activities and a space where to meet.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	16.60%	30.80%	52.60%
Central Greece/ Greece	40.00%	23.30%	36.60%
Hame/ Finland	30.10%	24.70%	45.20%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	16.10%	24.90%	59.00%
Monaghan/ Ireland	43.30%	23.00%	33.80%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	27.00%	32.40%	40.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	31.50%	27.80%	40.80%
Flanders/ Belgium	10.80%	24.70%	64.50%
Galilee/ Israel	8.30%	16.70%	75.00%
Apulia/ Italy	30.80%	30.80%	38.40%
North Macedonia	55.70%	19.50%	24.80%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	10.80%	24.70%	64.50%
	23.50%	25.30%	51.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities		
	This area offers quality commercial services such as restaurants, shops, car maintenance, etc.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	21.00%	17.20%	61.80%
Central Greece/ Greece	12.90%	41.90%	45.10%
Hame/ Finland	33.70%	13.50%	52.80%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	31.10%	17.60%	51.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	61.30%	8.00%	30.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	39.00%	17.10%	43.90%
Cuenca/ Spain	63.00%	24.10%	13.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	23.30%	13.60%	63.10%
Galilee/ Israel	20.00%	32.00%	48.00%
Apulia/ Italy	46.40%	28.60%	64.30%
North Macedonia	26.10%	18.30%	55.60%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	23.30%	13.60%	63.10%
	30.50%	17.50%	52.00%

PILOT / COUNTRY	2. Recreation / social activities		
	Recreation and social activities are important to me		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	3.80%	20.50%	75.70%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.50%	9.70%	83.90%
Hame/ Finland	8.00%	17.20%	74.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.30%	12.80%	84.80%
Monaghan/ Ireland	96.10%	3.90%	0.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	4.90%	22.00%	73.20%
Cuenca/ Spain	1.90%	1.90%	96.30%
Flanders/ Belgium	2.00%	12.90%	85.10%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	16.00%	84.00%
Apulia/ Italy	14.80%	40.70%	44.40%
North Macedonia	5.20%	7.00%	87.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	2.00%	12.90%	85.10%
	9.30%	13.40%	77.30%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living		
	Housing opportunities are adequate in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	26.90%	24.40%	48.80%
Central Greece/ Greece	10.00%	63.30%	26.70%
Hame/ Finland	20.90%	15.10%	63.90%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	67.30%	13.30%	19.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	26.70%	18.70%	54.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	19.50%	17.10%	63.40%
Cuenca/ Spain	31.50%	31.50%	37.10%
Flanders/ Belgium	5.90%	9.70%	84.50%
Galilee/ Israel	16.70%	25.00%	58.30%
Apulia/ Italy	21.70%	26.10%	52.20%
North Macedonia	23.50%	27.80%	48.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	5.90%	9.70%	84.50%
	35.90%	18.50%	45.60%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living		
	I am proud of living in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	11.70%	18.20%	70.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	6.40%	25.80%	67.80%
Hame/ Finland	5.80%	9.30%	84.90%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	4.20%	14.10%	81.80%
Monaghan/ Ireland	86.80%	6.60%	6.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	7.30%	92.70%
Cuenca/ Spain	1.90%	11.10%	87.10%
Flanders/ Belgium	3.90%	21.40%	74.80%
Galilee/ Israel	8.00%	4.00%	88.00%
Apulia/ Italy	8.00%	16.00%	76.00%
North Macedonia	15.30%	24.30%	60.30%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	3.90%	21.40%	74.80%
	11.20%	15.70%	73.10%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living		
	Living conditions (family development, air quality, accessibility, ...) are high		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	26.10%	21.70%	52.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.30%	30.00%	66.70%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	22.70%	24.50%	52.80%
Monaghan/ Ireland	63.20%	18.40%	18.40%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	14.60%	31.70%	53.60%
Cuenca/ Spain	18.50%	24.10%	57.40%
Flanders/ Belgium	10.70%	22.30%	66.90%
Galilee/ Israel	16.00%	8.00%	76.00%
Apulia/ Italy	15.40%	15.40%	69.20%
North Macedonia	27.50%	25.00%	47.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	10.70%	22.30%	66.90%
	22.90%	23.20%	53.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living		
	There are problems of integration with some population in the territory (Minorities, new comers....).		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	19.60%	30.10%	50.30%
Central Greece/ Greece	32.20%	25.80%	42.00%
Hame/ Finland	28.60%	40.50%	31.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	31.50%	40.30%	28.10%
Monaghan/ Ireland	75.40%	15.10%	9.50%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	51.30%	28.20%	20.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	58.90%	23.50%	17.60%
Flanders/ Belgium	38.00%	41.00%	21.00%
Galilee/ Israel	13.00%	34.80%	52.20%
Apulia/ Italy	25.90%	29.60%	44.40%
North Macedonia	44.20%	30.10%	25.60%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	38.00%	41.00%	21.00%
	36.20%	34.70%	29.10%

PILOT / COUNTRY	3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living		
	There are important social or political conflicts in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	38.30%	35.70%	26.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	53.40%	30.00%	16.60%
Hame/ Finland	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	62.00%	24.80%	13.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	48.70%	25.00%	26.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	82.00%	5.10%	12.90%
Cuenca/ Spain	67.90%	18.90%	13.20%
Flanders/ Belgium	58.70%	29.90%	11.30%
Galilee/ Israel	20.00%	28.00%	52.00%
Apulia/ Italy	33.30%	25.90%	40.70%
North Macedonia	28.70%	33.00%	38.30%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	58.70%	29.90%	11.30%
	53.00%	27.30%	19.70%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital		
	There are enough young people in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	20.50%	19.20%	60.30%
Central Greece/ Greece	19.40%	41.90%	38.70%
Hame/ Finland	57.90%	18.20%	23.90%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	51.30%	17.40%	31.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	55.20%	20.50%	24.40%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	12.20%	87.80%
Cuenca/ Spain	84.00%	10.70%	5.40%
Flanders/ Belgium	9.00%	20.00%	71.00%
Galilee/ Israel	48.00%	16.00%	36.00%
Apulia/ Italy	42.30%	15.40%	53.80%
North Macedonia	70.00%	9.40%	20.50%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	9.00%	20.00%	71.00%
	42.00%	17.60%	40.40%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital		
	There are enough women in the area.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	8.30%	29.90%	61.80%
Central Greece/ Greece	31.60%	57.90%	10.60%
Hame/ Finland	14.20%	41.20%	44.70%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	11.50%	26.10%	62.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	67.50%	24.70%	7.80%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	7.30%	92.60%
Cuenca/ Spain	57.10%	25.00%	17.90%
Flanders/ Belgium	0.00%	20.80%	79.20%
Galilee/ Israel	8.30%	41.70%	50.00%
Apulia/ Italy	19.20%	53.80%	26.90%
North Macedonia	43.50%	23.50%	33.00%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	0.00%	20.80%	79.20%
	18.00%	27.10%	54.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital		
	There are enough babies born in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	26.30%	32.70%	41.10%
Central Greece/ Greece	58.10%	19.40%	22.60%
Hame/ Finland	67.90%	26.20%	6.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	58.20%	18.40%	23.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	65.70%	26.30%	7.90%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	12.90%	7.70%	79.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	92.80%	3.60%	3.60%
Flanders/ Belgium	3.00%	28.30%	68.70%
Galilee/ Israel	17.40%	30.40%	52.20%
Apulia/ Italy	22.20%	40.70%	37.00%
North Macedonia	69.10%	15.00%	16.00%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	3.00%	28.30%	68.70%
	46.00%	22.20%	31.70%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital		
	There are enough working people to support the dependent population (i.e. children, elderly).		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	27.20%	26.00%	46.80%
Central Greece/ Greece	33.30%	23.30%	43.30%
Hame/ Finland	52.30%	26.10%	21.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	49.30%	22.50%	28.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	36.40%	36.40%	27.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	8.10%	5.40%	86.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	73.20%	12.50%	14.30%
Flanders/ Belgium	14.00%	24.00%	62.00%
Galilee/ Israel	40.00%	20.00%	40.00%
Apulia/ Italy	14.30%	46.40%	39.20%
North Macedonia	57.90%	11.40%	30.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	14.00%	24.00%	62.00%
	39.50%	22.80%	37.70%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital		
	Our community and voluntary sectors are well developed and address the social needs of our region and create opportunities.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	21.10%	44.10%	26.30%
Central Greece/ Greece	29.00%	58.10%	6.50%
Hame/ Finland	7.90%	18.00%	50.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	36.20%	31.90%	17.70%
Monaghan/ Ireland	47.40%	13.20%	22.40%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	30.60%	22.20%	38.90%
Cuenca/ Spain	37.70%	15.10%	7.50%
Flanders/ Belgium	10.30%	18.60%	52.60%
Galilee/ Israel	28.00%	28.00%	32.00%
Apulia/ Italy	18.50%	40.70%	33.30%
North Macedonia	50.00%	14.00%	14.90%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	10.30%	18.60%	52.60%
	29.30%	27.20%	27.30%

PILOT / COUNTRY	4. Demographic & human capital		
	It is possible to find opportunities to develop family plans.		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	12.20%	37.40%	50.40%
Central Greece/ Greece	22.60%	54.80%	22.60%
Hame/ Finland	16.30%	40.80%	42.90%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	28.00%	32.00%	40.00%
Monaghan/ Ireland	40.00%	25.30%	34.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	27.80%	30.60%	41.70%
Cuenca/ Spain	68.50%	13.00%	18.60%
Flanders/ Belgium	6.30%	20.00%	73.70%
Galilee/ Israel	33.40%	37.50%	29.20%
Apulia/ Italy	22.20%	40.70%	37.00%
North Macedonia	45.10%	32.70%	22.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	6.30%	20.00%	73.70%
	26.00%	30.80%	43.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	The area offers good opportunities for start-ups and creating new businesses		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	38.40%	35.10%	26.50%
Central Greece/ Greece	58.10%	29.00%	12.90%
Hame/ Finland	16.30%	36.50%	47.30%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	32.70%	30.00%	37.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	52.00%	24.00%	24.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	73.30%	13.30%	13.30%
Cuenca/ Spain	63.60%	9.10%	27.30%
Flanders/ Belgium	16.50%	20.60%	62.90%
Galilee/ Israel	64.00%	20.00%	16.00%
Apulia/ Italy	18.50%	44.40%	37.00%
North Macedonia	32.50%	24.80%	42.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	16.50%	20.60%	62.90%
	34.40%	27.30%	38.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	There are sources for financing innovative/new rural activities		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	42.20%	39.60%	18.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	25.90%	58.10%	16.10%
Hame/ Finland	18.40%	31.60%	50.00%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	28.80%	35.00%	36.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	52.00%	18.70%	29.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	52.80%	25.00%	22.20%
Cuenca/ Spain	62.50%	25.00%	12.50%
Flanders/ Belgium	12.10%	34.10%	53.90%
Galilee/ Israel	60.80%	21.70%	17.40%
Apulia/ Italy	22.70%	27.30%	50.00%
North Macedonia	38.30%	32.20%	29.60%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	12.10%	34.10%	53.90%
	32.50%	33.30%	34.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	There is an adequate special taxation scheme to attract new businesses in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	53.70%	38.80%	7.50%
Central Greece/ Greece	74.20%	22.60%	3.20%
Hame/ Finland	48.60%	36.50%	14.90%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	63.00%	30.60%	6.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	15.30%	37.50%	47.20%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	92.90%	3.60%	3.60%
Cuenca/ Spain	81.80%	10.90%	7.30%
Flanders/ Belgium	14.80%	65.40%	19.70%
Galilee/ Israel	52.10%	17.40%	30.40%
Apulia/ Italy	22.20%	40.70%	37.00%
North Macedonia	46.50%	37.10%	16.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	14.80%	65.40%	19.70%
	50.00%	36.30%	13.70%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	There are adequate services for entrepreneurial support and new business development with the provision of experienced services		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	41.70%	37.70%	20.50%
Central Greece/ Greece	58.10%	35.50%	6.50%
Hame/ Finland	19.20%	38.50%	42.30%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	44.20%	35.90%	19.90%
Monaghan/ Ireland	43.70%	25.40%	31.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	83.90%	6.50%	9.70%
Cuenca/ Spain	76.70%	10.70%	12.50%
Flanders/ Belgium	14.70%	47.70%	37.50%
Galilee/ Israel	56.50%	17.40%	26.10%
Apulia/ Italy	17.20%	41.40%	41.30%
North Macedonia	50.00%	33.60%	16.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	14.70%	47.70%	37.50%
	40.80%	35.00%	24.10%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	The area is good for new, innovative companies and creative professionals		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	23.40%	31.20%	45.40%
Central Greece/ Greece	48.40%	16.10%	35.50%
Hame/ Finland	31.70%	37.80%	30.40%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	24.80%	23.70%	51.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	43.20%	28.40%	28.40%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	59.40%	15.60%	25.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	16.70%	16.70%	66.60%
Flanders/ Belgium	15.90%	39.40%	44.60%
Galilee/ Israel	37.50%	20.80%	41.70%
Apulia/ Italy	28.60%	28.60%	46.50%
North Macedonia	48.70%	33.30%	17.90%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	15.90%	39.40%	44.60%
	28.70%	28.60%	42.70%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	The area favours eco-firms and sustainable business (circular economy)		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	40.40%	44.40%	15.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	22.60%	19.40%	58.10%
Hame/ Finland	31.60%	45.60%	22.80%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	29.60%	37.90%	32.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	19.20%	41.10%	39.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	63.70%	21.20%	15.10%
Cuenca/ Spain	31.50%	18.50%	50.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	46.90%	31.30%	21.90%
Galilee/ Israel	25.00%	50.00%	25.00%
Apulia/ Italy	31.00%	48.30%	20.60%
North Macedonia	12.80%	14.50%	72.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	46.90%	31.30%	21.90%
	32.40%	34.70%	32.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	There are enough possibilities for employment		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	38.90%	23.60%	37.60%
Central Greece/ Greece	64.50%	32.30%	3.20%
Hame/ Finland	61.30%	23.90%	14.80%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	62.20%	16.90%	21.00%
Monaghan/ Ireland	29.90%	14.30%	55.90%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	41.50%	14.60%	43.90%
Cuenca/ Spain	65.40%	20.00%	14.50%
Flanders/ Belgium	13.20%	24.50%	62.20%
Galilee/ Israel	92.00%	4.00%	4.00%
Apulia/ Italy	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
North Macedonia	41.00%	31.60%	27.30%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	13.20%	24.50%	62.20%
	47.30%	20.90%	31.80%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	The area offers possibilities for sustainable tourism (cultural heritage, nature, sports, local food, ...)		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	16.60%	22.90%	60.50%
Central Greece/ Greece	12.90%	29.00%	58.10%
Hame/ Finland	8.80%	17.60%	73.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	12.70%	19.10%	68.30%
Monaghan/ Ireland	59.30%	13.20%	27.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	7.50%	22.50%	70.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	14.30%	21.40%	64.30%
Flanders/ Belgium	14.90%	15.80%	69.40%
Galilee/ Israel	16.00%	12.00%	72.00%
Apulia/ Italy	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
North Macedonia	28.50%	22.40%	49.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	14.90%	15.80%	69.40%
	17.50%	19.20%	63.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	5. Business, economy & innovation		
	The area offers possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	18.50%	31.40%	50.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.70%	22.60%	67.80%
Hame/ Finland	3.60%	8.30%	88.10%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	9.30%	14.10%	76.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	55.30%	32.90%	11.80%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	8.60%	25.70%	65.70%
Cuenca/ Spain	9.10%	7.30%	83.60%
Flanders/ Belgium	25.20%	17.20%	57.60%
Galilee/ Israel	4.20%	25.00%	70.90%
Apulia/ Italy	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
North Macedonia	24.10%	20.70%	55.10%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	25.20%	17.20%	57.60%
	17.00%	18.80%	64.20%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas		
	Women and men equally participate in decision making and working life		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	23.70%	22.40%	53.90%
Central Greece/ Greece	10.30%	31.00%	58.60%
Hame/ Finland	7.90%	14.80%	77.30%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	19.60%	25.90%	54.40%
Monaghan/ Ireland	52.00%	18.70%	29.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	11.10%	16.70%	72.20%
Cuenca/ Spain	28.60%	19.60%	51.80%
Flanders/ Belgium	21.80%	21.80%	56.40%
Galilee/ Israel	36.00%	16.00%	48.00%
Apulia/ Italy	21.70%	43.50%	34.80%
North Macedonia	28.00%	25.40%	46.50%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	21.80%	21.80%	56.40%
	22.70%	23.20%	54.10%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas		
	Loneliness and isolation do not affect many people in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	28.80%	32.90%	38.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	41.30%	20.70%	37.90%
Hame/ Finland	57.30%	28.00%	14.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	53.00%	32.90%	14.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	9.10%	5.20%	85.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	10.00%	25.00%	65.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	55.30%	19.60%	25.00%
Flanders/ Belgium	37.40%	26.30%	36.40%
Galilee/ Israel	45.90%	20.80%	33.40%
Apulia/ Italy	23.00%	19.20%	57.70%
North Macedonia	50.90%	22.30%	26.80%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	37.40%	26.30%	36.40%
	42.40%	27.00%	30.50%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas		
	There are good opportunities for young people to participate in decision making		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	29.10%	32.30%	38.70%
Central Greece/ Greece	24.10%	55.20%	20.70%
Hame/ Finland	31.30%	25.30%	43.40%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	30.20%	35.20%	34.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	18.20%	29.90%	52.00%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.50%	15.00%	82.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	51.80%	19.60%	28.60%
Flanders/ Belgium	20.80%	25.70%	53.50%
Galilee/ Israel	33.40%	41.70%	25.00%
Apulia/ Italy	21.50%	28.60%	50.00%
North Macedonia	54.30%	29.30%	16.40%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	20.80%	25.70%	53.50%
	29.90%	30.80%	39.30%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas		
	In the area exists lively communities and citizen-driven local activities		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	22.00%	27.10%	51.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	53.60%	28.60%	17.90%
Hame/ Finland	8.00%	20.50%	71.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	20.80%	33.40%	45.70%
Monaghan/ Ireland	60.50%	19.70%	19.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	14.60%	17.10%	68.30%
Cuenca/ Spain	50.90%	20.00%	29.10%
Flanders/ Belgium	11.70%	26.20%	62.10%
Galilee/ Israel	12.50%	29.20%	58.30%
Apulia/ Italy	21.50%	21.40%	60.70%
North Macedonia	59.80%	29.90%	10.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	11.70%	26.20%	62.10%
	26.30%	27.80%	45.80%

PILOT / COUNTRY	6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas		
	There are good opportunities for women to participate in various social activities and working life in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	14.40%	36.60%	49.00%
Central Greece/ Greece	14.20%	32.10%	53.60%
Hame/ Finland	5.80%	14.00%	80.20%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	12.90%	20.80%	66.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	68.40%	15.80%	15.80%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	2.40%	12.20%	85.40%
Cuenca/ Spain	30.30%	30.40%	39.30%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.90%	16.50%	81.60%
Galilee/ Israel	25.00%	33.30%	41.60%
Apulia/ Italy	14.80%	25.90%	63.00%
North Macedonia	38.20%	20.00%	41.70%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.90%	16.50%	81.60%
	17.20%	21.90%	60.80%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity		
	The area has wide open landscapes or other beautiful nature scenery		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	4.40%	15.90%	79.60%
Central Greece/ Greece	3.20%	12.90%	83.90%
Hame/ Finland	1.10%	6.70%	92.30%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	3.20%	3.20%	93.60%
Monaghan/ Ireland	88.40%	6.50%	5.20%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	4.90%	14.60%	80.50%
Cuenca/ Spain	14.20%	12.50%	73.30%
Flanders/ Belgium	31.00%	12.60%	56.40%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	4.00%	96.00%
Apulia/ Italy	22.70%	22.70%	59.10%
North Macedonia	2.50%	10.20%	87.30%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	31.00%	12.60%	56.40%
	13.60%	8.80%	77.50%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity		
	Nature in the area is diverse		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	7.60%	12.70%	79.60%
Central Greece/ Greece	19.40%	25.80%	54.90%
Hame/ Finland	1.10%	7.80%	91.10%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	3.50%	4.10%	92.50%
Monaghan/ Ireland	81.10%	6.80%	12.20%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	14.60%	12.20%	73.10%
Cuenca/ Spain	7.30%	16.40%	76.40%
Flanders/ Belgium	32.00%	12.00%	56.00%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	4.00%	96.00%
Apulia/ Italy	8.60%	26.10%	65.20%
North Macedonia	3.30%	10.20%	86.50%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	32.00%	12.00%	56.00%
	14.00%	9.20%	76.90%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity		
	High Nature Value Areas (i.e. Natura 2000, Natural and National Parks) are well valorised in the area		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	23.60%	40.10%	36.20%
Central Greece/ Greece	9.70%	29.00%	61.30%
Hame/ Finland	13.40%	29.30%	57.30%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	12.60%	26.00%	61.40%
Monaghan/ Ireland	45.70%	18.60%	35.70%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	19.40%	25.80%	54.90%
Cuenca/ Spain	50.00%	30.80%	19.20%
Flanders/ Belgium	20.40%	30.60%	49.00%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	8.00%	92.00%
Apulia/ Italy	16.00%	20.00%	64.00%
North Macedonia	40.20%	19.70%	40.20%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	20.40%	30.60%	49.00%
	21.40%	27.50%	51.10%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity		
	Cultivation practices in the area are done in environmentally sound way		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	31.60%	43.20%	25.10%
Central Greece/ Greece	20.60%	58.60%	20.60%
Hame/ Finland	9.40%	27.10%	63.60%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	22.40%	32.00%	45.70%
Monaghan/ Ireland	25.30%	32.00%	42.60%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	60.00%	25.00%	15.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	22.20%	29.60%	48.10%
Flanders/ Belgium	45.90%	31.60%	22.50%
Galilee/ Israel	12.50%	33.30%	54.20%
Apulia/ Italy	17.80%	42.90%	39.30%
North Macedonia	43.90%	24.60%	31.50%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	45.90%	31.60%	22.50%
	29.50%	32.90%	37.50%

PILOT / COUNTRY	7. Environment & Biodiversity		
	Environment and landscapes are important to me		
	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Slovakia	3.10%	5.70%	91.10%
Central Greece/ Greece	0.00%	12.90%	87.10%
Hame/ Finland	1.10%	1.10%	97.80%
Vidzeme/ Latvia	2.30%	2.50%	95.20%
Monaghan/ Ireland	96.00%	2.60%	1.30%
Central Bohemia/ Czechia	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Cuenca/ Spain	3.60%	3.60%	92.80%
Flanders/ Belgium	1.00%	1.00%	98.10%
Galilee/ Israel	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%
Apulia/ Italy	14.80%	29.60%	55.50%
North Macedonia	2.50%	2.50%	94.90%
Mazowieckie/ Poland	1.00%	1.00%	98.10%
	8.00%	3.30%	88.70%

Annex 3 Responses to monitors' comments

Comments made by the monitors	Explanation
<p>Overall: long report with presentation of needs assessment from the different study areas.</p> <p>This deliverable has the potential to be very interesting in that it does in fact demonstrate the way in which rural areas are differentiated - something that was not acknowledged in the connected deliverable D1.1 (the main literature review). The data on p. 16 is very revealing on this matter. Further, it unpacks the idea of attractiveness, quality of life and wellbeing.</p>	<p>D1.1 supplemented with text about rural diversity, rural attractiveness in different contexts, and summary of literature review.</p>
<p>This Deliverable does not seem to map onto other deliverables in this work package. References to and linkages with the other WPs (WP2 and WP4) would help to understand the role of this first SWOT prepared under different conditions (lacking staff in some teams, establishment of a relationship with the key persons of the study areas, Corona restrictions in 2020 etc.) and show how different activities complement one another. A critical reflection on work in progress as seen in D1.6 is lacking.</p>	<p>D1.4 no linkage with WP2 (text mining). D1.4 is strong linkage with WP4 because D1.4 is based on pilot survey and interviews.</p> <p>Reference to WP4 added in methodology section.</p> <p>Reference to D1.6 not taken into account as it is not directly linked with rural attractiveness.</p> <p>Links with T4.3, 4.4 are mentioned in summary, Introduction, and in sections 1, 2, 3, 4.</p>
<p>A few issues regarding the overarching methodological approach and state of the art of regional development in rural areas will profit from a sharpening, and some details need to be reviewed. Table 1 and Table 2 are not fully in line with the presentation of pilot areas on www.polirural.eu (Nitra/Slovenia, Segobriga/Cuenca, Spain, and Strumica-Gevgenija/North Macedonia). The section 1.1. (Methodology) lacks a description of the stakeholder mapping and the set-up of the methodological foundation for the participatory regional development process (representation of e.g., rural industries with farming, crafts, service, representation of social needs (NGOs, public agencies), nature conservation, structural conditions (transport, broadband, food processing) etc.</p>	<p>The revised version corrected as pilot regions were changed. New regions' data inseted in methodology section and section 2 Characteristics and comparison of PoliRural pilot regions.</p> <p>Methodology of stakeholder mapping was elaborated in task T4.2. Reference added in methodology section.</p> <p>Methodological section has been expanded with information on the interconnection of tasks and deliverables, explanation links with D1.1. rurall development contexts</p>
<p>Several issues listed in particular needs are very specific (thematic parks, support of startups). The interpretation of this data requires a transparent presentation of the key persons or agencies involved. While some topics identified are very specific, other answers sound rather general.</p>	<p>No action needed as these needs come from participants and regions are very different in scale and specificity.</p>
<p>Comparative work is tricky for several reasons a) the administrative level of the study areas are very different (e.g. Nuts1=Flanders, SK; Nuts 2=HL, MK, PL; Nuts3=ES, and Nuts 4 in FI and IE); needs will differ systematically between the NUTS perspectives and responsible target groups involved in the SWOT. b) The selection process of relevant regional development sectors with relating policy areas and programmes vary between pilots.</p>	<p>This is a choice of project partners, as there are different aims in particular regions. This should be seen as an advantage of the project, as it allows to see different levels and contexts.</p> <p>The stakeholder involvement processes within the pilots based on D1.3 and T4.2 (Reference added in Methodology section)</p>